

Towards sustainable crop protection in agriculture: A framework for research and policy

Robert Finger^{a,*}, Jaap Sok^b, Emmanuel Ahovi^b, Sharmin Akter^{a,i}, Johan Bremmer^j, Silke Dachbrodt-Saaydeh^c, Carolien de Lauwere^j, Cordelia Kreft^a, Per Kudsk^d, Fatima Lambarraa-Lehnhardt^e, Chloe McCallum^{a,f}, Alfons Oude Lansink^b, Erwin Wauters^g, Niklas Möhring^h

^a *ETH Zürich, Agricultural Economics and Policy Group, Zürich, Switzerland*

^b *Business Economics Group, Wageningen University and Research, Wageningen, the Netherlands*

^c *Julius Kühn-Institut, Kleinmachnow, Germany*

^d *Aarhus University, Slagelse, Denmark*

^e *Leibniz-Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF), Germany & University of Göttingen, Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development, Göttingen, Germany*

^f *Queens University Belfast, United Kingdom*

^g *Institute for Agricultural and Fisheries Research (ILVO), Social Sciences Unit, Mellebeke, Belgium*

^h *Production Economics Group, University of Bonn, Bonn, Germany*

ⁱ *Department of Agricultural Statistics, Sylhet Agricultural University, Bangladesh*

^j *Wageningen Economic Research, Transition Risk and Innovation Governance, Wageningen, the Netherlands*

HIGHLIGHTS

- The adoption of sustainable crop protection practices is needed to meet ambitious targets for reducing the risk of pesticide use.
- We provide new insights into farmer decision-making and policy analysis towards more sustainable crop protection approaches.
- Definitions of adoption need to move from simple adoption metrics to impacts, for example on pesticide risk reduction.
- Behavioural factors are highly relevant to farmers' sustainable crop protection decisions, but are currently under-researched.
- Our analysis will help guide policy decisions to achieve pesticide use and risk reduction targets.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

* Corresponding author at: ETH Zürich, Agricultural Economics and Policy Group, Sonneggstrasse 33, 8092 Zürich, Switzerland.
E-mail address: rofinger@ethz.ch (R. Finger).

ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Laurens Klerkx

Keywords:

Pesticides
Integrated pest management
Sustainable crop protection
Farmer behaviour
Agricultural policy

ABSTRACT

CONTEXT: European countries have set ambitious targets to reduce the risks of pesticide use. Achieving these targets will require a large proportion of farmers to adopt sustainable crop protection practices. However, how to enable this transition and what are the best policies to support farmers remain open questions.

OBJECTIVE: Here, we provide a coherent review of existing evidence and new insights into farmer decision-making and policy analysis in the context of the transition to more sustainable crop protection. We synthesise and extend the empirical evidence and the conceptual and methodological foundations to examine farmers' decisions to adopt sustainable crop protection and to assess the potential of different policy measures to support this transition. Our analysis focuses on European agriculture.

METHODS: We provide a framework and synthesise evidence by reviewing the literature and combining agronomic and economic perspectives. We focus on three issues: i) indicators for empirical analyses of adoption of sustainable crop protection practices; ii) behavioural perspectives on farmer adoption; iii) insights into methodological approaches for assessing adoption of sustainable crop protection practices and related policies.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION: We have identified four main findings and implications. First, sustainable crop protection practices consist of combinations and bundles of individual measures that are not currently regularly considered in policy instruments and policy analysis. Second, definitions of adoption should move from simple adoption metrics to impacts, for example on pesticide risk reduction. Third, behavioural factors are highly relevant to farmers' adoption decisions, but are currently under-researched and under-represented in the field of sustainable crop protection practices. Fourth, the tools currently used for policy analysis do not allow these key aspects to be represented. We draw policy conclusions.

SIGNIFICANCE: Our analyses help guide policy decisions to achieve pesticide use and risk reduction objectives, and have implications for pesticide policy in Europe and beyond. We identify gaps in current conceptual and methodological approaches, promising avenues for future research, and ways to make results more coherent and comparable. Our analysis thus provides new insights and templates to guide future research and policy analysis on the adoption of sustainable crop protection approaches.

1. Introduction

Reducing pesticide use and risks is a key policy objective (Schneider et al., 2023; Finger, 2024a). While effective pest management is crucial for food production and the economic viability of the agricultural sector, current levels of pesticide use in agriculture contribute to the decline of biodiversity, have negative impacts on public health (e.g. Tang et al., 2021; Tsiafouli et al., 2015; Wuepper et al., 2023a), and even threaten long-term agricultural productivity (e.g. Skevas et al., 2013). The European Union aims to reduce the use and risks of pesticides in general by 50% by 2030, and to reduce the use of more hazardous pesticides by 50% (EU Commission, 2020; Schebesta and Candel, 2020; Schneider et al., 2023).¹ To achieve these policy goals, a large proportion of farmers will need to adopt alternative crop protection approaches to reduce current levels of pesticide use, and these alternatives will need to be effective and economically viable. Various sustainable crop protection approaches have been proposed and promoted worldwide for decades (e.g. Barzman et al., 2015; Parsa et al., 2014; Waddington et al., 2014). However, the actual implementation of sustainable crop protection approaches in Europe remains limited and far below what is required to meet ambitious pesticide use and risk reduction targets (e.g. European Court of Auditors, 2020; Deguine et al., 2021; Lefebvre et al., 2015; Parsa et al., 2014). How to unlock the large potential of sustainable crop protection approaches and how to define effective and efficient policies to support farmer adoption remain open questions.

In this paper, we provide a coherent overview of existing evidence and new insights into farmer decision-making and policy analysis in the context of shifting to more sustainable crop protection practices. We

¹ It should be noted, however, that the sustainable use of pesticides to achieve these strategic objectives was rejected by the European Parliament in December 2023 and withdrawn by the European Commission in February Möhring et al., 2024 (Finger et al., 2024a). Other European countries, such as Switzerland, have also adopted ambitious risk targets for pesticide use (see e.g. Finger, 2021). Pesticide reduction was also addressed at the UN Biodiversity Summit (COP15), and international targets for a 50% reduction in pesticide risk were set in the post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework of the Convention on Biological Diversity (Candel et al., 2023; Möhring et al., 2023a).

review and extend the conceptual and methodological foundations for studying farmers' decisions to adopt sustainable crop protection and for assessing the potential of different policy measures. We propose standards to unify ongoing research in several countries, identify gaps in conceptual and methodological approaches, and highlight promising avenues for future research.

Various approaches and concepts have been developed to reduce pesticide use and risk, such as integrated pest management, agroecological crop protection, and organic agriculture and pesticide-free (but non-organic) production systems (Barzman et al., 2015; Jacquet et al., 2022; Deguine et al., 2021; Meemken and Qaim, 2018; Finger and Möhring, 2024).² Here, we do not focus on a specific concept or approach, but more generally on the adoption behaviour of *sustainable crop protection approaches* (see Möhring et al., 2024 and Section 2 for a definition). Our reasoning is that the above concepts and approaches share the goal of minimising the use of pesticides that are harmful to the environment and human health, and can therefore all be used (alone or in combination) to achieve policy goals. For example, by adopting an integrated approach combining prevention and control of pests and diseases, and by giving preference to non-chemical, such as biological and physical methods of pest and disease control. The common goal of these integrated approaches is to ensure effective pest management and high productivity in food production, to reduce environmental impacts and minimise impacts on human health, and to ensure the economic viability of agriculture. To this end, these approaches may allow for no

² It should be noted that in the context of European Union policies, integrated pest management in particular is considered a key concept to reduce the risk of pesticide use in conventional farming systems (Lefebvre et al., 2015; Barzman et al., 2015). In addition, the Farm to Fork strategy aims to increase the share of organic farming in the European Union to 25% by 2023 (Schebesta and Candel, 2020).

(i.e. organic and pesticide-free agriculture) or minimal use of synthetic chemical pesticides³ (e.g. integrated pest management, agroecological crop protection). This can be achieved by relying mainly on a mix of measures such as prevention, biological control, agronomic solutions (e.g. adapted crop rotations, field hygiene), technical solutions (e.g. mechanical weed control, smart farming) and the use of resistant and adapted varieties (Möhrling et al., 2020a, 2023a). Different approaches may also have similar impacts on farmer adoption (e.g. due to different adoption requirements, costs, benefits and risks). The basics of sustainable crop protection are defined and discussed in more detail in section 2.

There is a large body of literature defining and discussing sustainable crop protection practices for agricultural systems (e.g. Barzman et al., 2015; Deguine et al., 2021, 2023; Parsa et al., 2014; Owen et al., 2015). Various studies have provided assessments of the impacts of such practices, e.g. on farm economic performance (e.g. income and income risks), crop yields and yield variability, and potential impacts on the environment and human health (e.g. Midingoyi et al., 2019; Cuyuno et al., 2001; Kudsk and Jensen, 2014). Along these lines, many studies have examined different aspects of the economics of pesticide use, such as the costs, benefits and economic risks of pest management (e.g. Sexton et al., 2007; Waterfield and Zilberman, 2012; Osteen and Fernandez-Cornejo, 2013). In addition, previous research has examined farmer adoption of sustainable crop protection practices.⁴ For example, Lefebvre et al. (2015) provided an overview of European farmers' decisions regarding integrated pest management, highlighting the importance of cost-effectiveness, price premiums and farmers' attitudes. Gent et al. (2011) reviewed the role of risk and farmers' risk aversion for integrated pest management. Möhrling and Finger (2022) analysed the role of socio-economic, environmental and behavioural characteristics for adoption decisions towards pesticide-free (but not organic) wheat production systems.⁵ However, three major gaps remain in the literature.

First, an important limitation of the empirical literature on the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices is that most studies do not consider key agronomic and technical features of their implementation. Adoption is often analysed in a binary way (or only considers individual measures) (e.g. Shiferaw et al., 2008; Zachmann et al., 2023). However, effective substitution of pesticides usually requires matching bundles of measures (or portfolios, e.g. Bailey et al., 2009; Weltin et al., 2021) and often implies fundamental changes in whole cropping systems. Considering only binary decisions (full adoption/non-adoption) or the adoption of some measures of these bundles does not reflect the reality of farmer decision making in terms of potentially different and non-linear (additive) marginal adoption costs, benefits and risks. Adoption of 'only' a large proportion of the recommended alternative measures, as opposed to adoption of all measures, can be critical in terms of pesticide use and pesticide risk reduction. Furthermore, the current focus is often on the adoption of specific measures by farmers, but the potentially heterogeneous impacts of these decisions, e.g. on the environment and human health, are usually not considered. In

³ Note that we are aware that pesticides used in organic farming can also be harmful to the environment (e.g. copper). On the other hand, not all low-risk active substances that pose low risks to human health and the environment can be used in organic farming. Ultimately, therefore, the focus should be on risk reduction, regardless of whether pesticides can be used in organic farming or not.

⁴ In addition, there is a large literature on the adoption of new agricultural practices in general, see e.g. Pannell et al., 2006, Knowler and Bradshaw, 2007, Prokopy et al., 2008, Baumgart-Getz et al., 2012, Junyu Lu et al. 2022, Kuehne et al., 2017), see also section 4.

⁵ While we mainly focus on the farm level in our analysis here, the agricultural and food system perspective is key for such a transition to sustainable crop protection (e.g. Möhrling et al., 2020a, see also Oude Lansink et al., 2018, Rodenburg et al., 2015 and Schut et al., 2014 for examples).

summary, we lack an empirical definition and operationalisation of sustainable crop management and its impact on pesticide risk reduction for research and policy applications.

Second, farmer behavioural factors influencing the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices are underexplored. Recent studies highlight the relevance of a wide range of behavioural factors such as preferences, perceptions, personality and social networks to explain and predict farmers' behaviour in general (e.g. Dessart et al., 2019; Schaub et al., 2023; Wuepper et al., 2023b; Thompson et al., 2024). These factors are also likely to be particularly relevant for sustainable crop management. For example, pest management decisions are associated with high uncertainty and the efficacy of new pest management measures is often largely unknown in advance (e.g. Möhrling et al., 2020b). Thus, perceptions, attitudes, preferences and personality influence farmers' pest management decisions (e.g. Bakker et al., 2021; Finger and Möhrling, 2022; Knapp et al., 2021). To date, a coherent analysis of the potential role of these behavioural factors for (i) explaining the heterogeneity in the adoption of sustainable crop protection approaches across different production systems and socio-ecological contexts and (ii) the effectiveness and efficiency of policies aimed at reducing the risks of pesticide use is lacking.

Third, another gap is the lack of a coherent methodological framework to study farmers' adoption of sustainable crop protection practices and policies. Existing studies use different methodological approaches, including surveys, interviews, econometric analysis, and optimisation and simulation models applied at the field, farm or regional level (e.g. Rebaudo et al., 2014; Fan et al., 2020; Lefebvre et al., 2015; Song and Swinton, 2009; Möhrling and Finger, 2022). The interrelationships between these approaches, and their potential combination to support policy analysis, remain unexplored. There is a lack of guidance on how to leverage research from different countries and case studies, and how to relate findings from different methodologies. In addition, the currently dominant methodologies do not take into account the above-mentioned aspects of uptake definitions and behavioural factors. Therefore, methodological innovations are needed to assess farmers' behaviour and policies.

We contribute to the literature by: i) proposing appropriate and widely applicable indicators for empirical analyses of the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices; ii) providing a coherent conceptual and behavioural framework for the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices by farmers; iii) providing insights into how methodological approaches used to assess the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices and related policies can be improved. Our analysis focuses particularly on European agriculture because of its relevance to the achievement of pesticide policy objectives.⁶ Our analysis also provides a template to guide future research and policy analysis on the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices, making results more coherent and comparable. It will therefore help to guide policy decisions to achieve the pesticide use and risk reduction objectives of European countries, with implications for global pesticide policy.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. First, we provide a background on sustainable crop protection approaches and how they differ from conventional crop protection. Second, we discuss how to quantify and measure farmer adoption of sustainable crop protection practices. Third, we develop a framework for farmer adoption of sustainable crop protection approaches and review the empirical evidence. In particular, we highlight the role of farmer behavioural factors in adoption and identify knowledge gaps. Fourth, we summarise methods

⁶ European agriculture also shares similar policy measures, such as agri-environmental schemes, to steer farmers' behaviour, and farmers therefore face a similar decision-making environment. Extending the scope to other regions would introduce further confounding factors. This paper is also the basis for empirical work to be carried out in the Horizon Europe project 'Supporting UPtake Integrated Pest Management and lOW-risk pesTicide Use' (SUPPORT).

for assessing farmer behaviour, evaluate policies in the context of sustainable crop protection approaches, and provide insights for future methodological developments. Finally, we draw conclusions to provide insights and ways forward for policy and research.

2. Agronomic and economic background on sustainable crop protection approaches

Following Möhring et al. (2024), we define sustainable crop protection as individual or bundles of agricultural measures that aim to protect crops while reducing current dependence on pesticides and the risks associated with their use. These agricultural measures can reflect integrated or agro-ecological pest management paradigms and are, for example, the basis for organic and pesticide-free (but not organic) production, where synthetic pesticides are not allowed. Of these, integrated pest management (IPM) and organic farming have received the most political support in Europe to date. IPM should follow a set of general IPM principles (e.g. Barzman et al., 2015), which became mandatory for EU farmers in January 2014. However, the overall uptake of IPM in European farming systems is still quite limited (European Court of Auditors, 2020). In Table 1, we provide an overview of the main characteristics of the main systems that fall under our definition of sustainable crop protection.

The Efficiency, Substitution, Redesign framework (Hill and MacRae, 1996) can serve as a conceptual guide to how a transition to more sustainable crop protection systems can be achieved in Europe (see also Möhring et al., 2020a; Finger, 2021). Increasing the efficiency of current practices and substitution with other (existing) practices can lead to reductions in pesticide use in the short to medium term. Substitution aims to replace harmful pesticide use with alternatives. However, more substantial reductions in the medium to long term often require the redesign of current production systems to make them less vulnerable to pests (Finger, 2021).

A key difference between IPM and agroecological crop protection, on the one hand, and organic and pesticide-free production, on the other, is that the former are based on a set of recommendations or principles (e.g. eight IPM principles, see Barzman et al., 2015) that suggest best practices based on the production context. They aim to limit pesticide use to levels that are ‘economically and ecologically justified’ (pesticides that can be harmful to humans and the environment should be considered as a last resort). Agroecological crop protection has a particularly strong focus on non-chemical solutions, favouring natural solutions such as prevention and natural enemies of pests (Deguine et al., 2023). The recommendations of IPM and agroecological crop protection give farmers flexibility to adapt to local production conditions and pest pressures. Bundles or portfolios of alternative measures are often required to achieve similar levels of efficacy and yield as pesticide use (the concept of ‘many small hammers’, Liebman and Gallandt, 1997). Despite its original intentions, IPM as currently practised is mostly an example of substitution (e.g. Deguine et al., 2021). Farmers are looking for alternatives, or combinations of alternatives, to replace pesticides without having to substantially change and redesign their production systems. This is despite the fact that the first of the eight IPM principles deals with prevention and suppression, which should intuitively lead farmers to consider redesigning their farming systems. Agroecological crop protection has a stronger emphasis on redesign at field, landscape and regional levels. However, there are very few, if any, examples of widespread adoption of agroecological crop protection practices in the EU to date (Deguine et al., 2023; Ewert et al., 2023). In general, adherence to both principles may be legally mandated (e.g. as IPM currently is in the European Union), but is usually difficult to control due to its context-dependent nature. Furthermore, compliance is only rewarded if there are (regional) labels, which are rare for integrated or agroecological crop protection (e.g. Finger and Möhring, 2024).

Organic and pesticide-free production are both based on a set of fixed rules (e.g. no use of synthetic chemical pesticides) that are mandatory

for compliance with the production system. Exceptions are based on national specifications and include, for example, some pesticides such as copper and sulphur, and biological products (see Finger, 2024b for further discussions). Compliance is rewarded with a combination of public direct payments (widespread for organic; for pesticide-free only in Switzerland and Germany) and price premiums (from labels) (Finger and Möhring, 2024; Möhring and Finger, 2022; Crowder and Reganold, 2015). To maintain crop protection levels (without using pesticides), farmers also rely on crop protection strategies from the IPM or agro-ecological toolbox, but under the strict condition that they cannot combine them with synthetic pesticides. These key differences between recommendation- and rule-based systems also have potential implications for farmers’ decision-making and behaviour in adopting sustainable crop protection, and are considered in the following sections.

2.1. Examples of sustainable crop protection practices

In order to understand farmers’ choices and challenges in (adopting) sustainable crop protection, it is important to keep in mind the basic concepts and logic of crop protection against weeds, fungi and insect pests. Three relevant and illustrative examples for European agriculture are presented below.

Example 1. Herbicide use in arable crops. Herbicides are the most widely used weed control measure. In conventional agriculture, the application of herbicides is routine, in contrast to the use of fungicides and insecticides (Jørgensen et al., 2019). One of the reasons for this practice is the potential long-term effect of seed shedding on the occurrence of weeds in subsequent crops. To reduce herbicide use in arable crops, it is imperative that measures are taken to reduce weed populations to levels where they pose little or no risk to the current and subsequent crops. One of the most efficient ways for farmers to achieve this is through diversified crop rotation (Adeux et al., 2019; Guinet et al., 2023). Other measures available to farmers include increasing crop density, using competitive varieties, changing sowing dates and patterns, and planting weed-suppressing cover crops between main crops.⁷ Often none of these measures is sufficient on its own, but in combination they can be very effective (Riemens et al., 2022). If the combined effect of preventive and cultural methods is effective and reduces weed infestations to low levels, herbicide use may be omitted altogether and replaced by mechanical weeding methods such as harrowing. The efficacy of mechanical weeding is often significantly lower than that of herbicides (although it can increase with the number of passes), but if the weed infestation is low, a lower level of control can be accepted because the number of weeds surviving the treatment and affecting the crop yield will be low. This example illustrates that substitutes for pesticides may be readily available, but that bundles of measures are required to substitute for herbicide use, and this should be taken into account when analysing farmers’ adoption decisions.

Example 2. Fungicide use in apple production. Fungal diseases are a major constraint in apple production systems and fungicides make up the majority of pesticides used on apples. Apples are susceptible to several diseases such as apple scab (*Venturia inaequalis*), powdery mildew (*Podosphaera leucotricha*) and European canker (*Nectria galligena*), but fungicides are mainly used to control apple scab. Apple scab reduces both fruit yield and quality. Before the introduction of IPM, apple orchards were treated weekly until fruit setting and then every 2–3 weeks to prevent apple scab, resulting in 15–25 applications of preventative fungicides per year (Holb, 2009). With the introduction of

⁷ More recently, harvest weed seed control (seeds are collected or destroyed at harvest) has been widely adopted in Australia as a measure to reduce weed infestation (Walsh et al., 2017), but this technology has not been widely used under European conditions, which may be more challenging (Akhter et al., 2023).

Table 1
Overview of sustainable crop protection approaches and systems.

Name	Enforce-ment	Guiding principle crop protection	Compensa-tion	Implemen-tation	Impact on pesticide reduction targets
Integrated pest management	Obligatory (e.g. in European Union) participation - but recommendation based.	Eight principles (Barzman et al., 2015) - pesticides should be kept to levels that are 'economically and ecologically justified'. Mostly substitution of pesticides. Context dependent.	Usually no monetary compensation(except for labels, which are rarely used).	Widely known and part of cross compliance. Actual spread and adoption of "sound" practices is hard to monitor and assess.	IPM is intended to reduce pesticide risk but does not always do so.
Agroecological pest management	Voluntary participation - recommendation based	Using natural solutions based on agroecological principles to protect crops - no or very little pesticide use. Importance of redesign across scales. Context-dependent.	Usually no monetary compensation(except for labels, which are rarely used).	Actual spread and adoption of "sound" practices is hard to monitor and assess.	"Sound" adoption reduces pesticide use and risk.
Organic	Voluntary participation - rule-based.	Use of synthetic pesticides is prohibited - usually farm-level adoption.	Area subsidy (e.g., EU) and price premium under label (if certified).	EU average adoption 9.6% of farmland (controlled by governments/label organisations)	Adoption reduces pesticide use and risk.
Pesticide-free	Voluntary participation - rule-based.	Use of synthetic pesticides is prohibited - crop or crop-rotation level adoption.	Area subsidy and price premium under label.	Emerging in Switzerland, Germany and France (for example, in Switzerland, already ~15% for Swiss wheat) - controlled by governments/label organisations	Adoption reduces pesticide use and risk.

Note: Key references as follows: IPM (Barzman et al., 2015; Deguine et al., 2021), Agroecological crop protection (Deguine et al., 2023; Ewert et al., 2023), Organic agriculture (Crowder and Reganold, 2015; Meemken and Qaim, 2018), Pesticide-free production (Möhrling and Finger, 2022; Finger, 2024b; Finger and Möhrling, 2024).

IPM in the 1980s, the number of treatments was reduced by 30 to 50%. IPM strategies were based on an improved methodology for predicting apple scab infection periods, a better understanding of apple scab epidemiology and the marketing of more effective curative fungicides (Holb, 2009). So-called advanced IPM systems were subsequently developed, incorporating biological control agents (Carisse and Rolland, 2004) and sanitation procedures to reduce disease pressure (Sutton et al., 2000). Biological control of fungal diseases in apples has received much attention, but its use in conventional apple production is still limited due to low efficacy (Passey and Xu, 2019). However, the current over-reliance on fungicides has led to widespread resistance to the two most widely used groups of fungicides (Chapman et al., 2011; Xu et al., 2010) and there is an urgent need to rethink management practices. Important host resistance genes are available and have been incorporated into commercial apple cultivars, but this has broken down often in the past (Roberts and Crute, 1994; Patocchi et al., 2020). An alternative strategy is to incorporate several key resistance genes into the same cultivar ('pyramiding'), and this strategy has been shown to increase resistance levels (Laloi et al., 2017). Another potential approach is cultivar mixing, i.e. growing more than one cultivar in an orchard (Parisi et al., 2013). Cultivar mixtures cannot prevent apple scab, but reduce disease pressure and can be part of novel IPM strategies (Passey and Xu, 2019). Apple is a perennial crop and an orchard is typically productive for around 20 years, so changes to more sustainable production systems using resistant varieties or cultivar mixtures will take longer to implement than for annual crops. Compared to weed control, depending on the crop and disease, farmers also have to apply methods against fungal pathogens preventively (to prevent infestations) under uncertainty about the onset and pressure of infestations, which increases the importance of perceptions and preferences for these decisions (e.g. Möhrling et al., 2020b). Prediction and decision support systems help to reduce these uncertainties and thus reduce pesticide use. This example highlights both the importance of variety and cultivar choice and the importance of decisions under uncertainty, e.g. regarding the timing of measures for farmers.

Example 3. Insecticide use in oilseed rape production. Insect pests are a major challenge in many crops. In Europe, oilseed rape production accounts for a significant proportion of total insecticide use. In winter oilseed rape (*Brassica napus* L.), insects such as *Psylliodes chrysocephalus* L. and *Phyllotreta nemorum* L./*Phyllotreta undulata* L. cause

considerable damage to young seedlings in autumn. Pest monitoring and the use of economic thresholds are therefore essential, especially in view of the decreasing availability of insecticides and the increasing problems of insecticide resistance. Preventive measures such as later sowing and increasing crop density can reduce infestations (Kathage et al., 2018), but the milder autumn weather conditions recorded recently prolong feeding and oviposition, which may reduce the effectiveness of these measures. Early sowing to avoid feeding damage can also lead to increased oviposition and severe larval damage before winter (Ortega-Ramos et al., 2022). Conservation biocontrol methods such as off-field management options and companion or 'nurse' crops appear to contribute to reduced pest damage (Breitenmoser et al., 2020; Verret et al., 2017; White et al., 2020). Alternative control methods can be used to control pollen beetles in spring, including trap crops, push-pull methods (Cook et al., 2013), or crop margin management with flower-rich field margins or banker plants to support natural enemies (Skeltern and Cook, 2018). Natural antagonists such as parasitoid wasps (reviewed by Ulber et al., 2010) may offer an overlooked potential contribution to pollen beetle control. A systemic approach is essential, as soil management practices and insecticide applications need to be adapted to ensure overwintering and feeding of natural enemies such as parasitoids in the absence of the host. This example highlights the importance of a holistic approach to management practices at farm or even landscape level for effective and efficient sustainable crop protection.

This section has highlighted the difficulties in defining the uptake and impact of sustainable crop protection practices, given their heterogeneity and context dependency, as illustrated by the three examples. An appropriate definition and measurement of uptake is therefore a prerequisite for analysing farmers' decisions to adopt sustainable crop protection and for designing effective policies. We will therefore discuss appropriate metrics in the next section.

3. Suitable indicators for assessing the uptake of sustainable crop protection approaches

A key challenge for empirical and policy analysis of adoption of sustainable crop protection is the definition of uptake.⁸ By defining the uptake variable, we also define the understanding of when - and to what extent - a farmer has actually adopted sustainable crop protection. Furthermore, the (potential) uptake variable will usually serve as the dependent variable in the empirical analysis and thus as a measure of success for policy (analysis). Its definition is therefore crucial for reconciling research objectives (e.g. identifying determinants of pesticide risk reduction) and the actual impact of the outcome variable. Failure to choose a dependent variable that is consistent with the research objectives could actually lead to biased or even misleading findings on farmer adoption behaviour and subsequent policy recommendations. In this section, we discuss and provide practical guidance on the selection of appropriate variables. This may also serve as a template for the selection of appropriate variables for other researchers working on related research questions. Using similar arguments and variables to address related research questions will help to combine and replicate findings across countries and case studies. There are three main challenges in defining appropriate adoption variables.

First, the choice of an effective and efficient sustainable crop protection strategy depends on the production context. The definition of uptake or uptake intensity can therefore vary according to crop, farm type, region and environmental and weather conditions. As environmental and weather conditions can change between and within growing seasons, an effective and efficient crop protection strategy can also change between and within growing seasons. Second, the pathway between the adoption of practices and their actual impact on pesticide risk reduction (the ultimate policy objective) depends on a wide range of context-specific factors, such as the production, environmental or institutional context (see Fig. 1 in section 4 for an overview) and the indicators used. Different indicators will be more or less directly linked to pesticide risk reduction. Third, pest management practices are often interdependent, and their effectiveness and efficiency may therefore change in a non-linear way when combined. The uptake of different bundles of measures may therefore be assessed differently from the uptake of individual measures or other combinations of practices. In addition, we often do not know well enough what farmers are doing, how and where: accurate and timely data on pesticide use are scarce (Mesnage et al., 2021), and the availability of data on the uptake of sustainable crop protection practices (e.g. preventive or direct non-chemical methods) is even more limited (Möhring et al., 2024). Data scarcity can therefore severely constrain the choice of uptake variables in research and policy analysis, making it necessary to deviate from the choice of the first best indicator.

In Table 2, we provide a practical overview of different types of adoption indicators, as well as recommendations on their suitability for specific types of research questions or settings, the data and methods required, and typical applications and access to databases. Recommendations also apply to studies that base their outcome variables on intentions or stated choices. These studies should also design their survey instrument so that the decision situation presented is realistic and policy relevant. The indicator types are listed in order of their link to actual impacts on pesticide risk reduction (from weakest at the top to strongest at the bottom). Depending on data availability, a stronger link should normally be preferred.

The first type of indicator presented in Table 2 provides information on the (intensity of) uptake. The definition of uptake is simpler for production systems that strictly exclude the use of certain types or all

⁸ Note that we do not explicitly distinguish between 'adoption' and 'implementation' of practices, but refer to 'adoption' as the whole process from information to implementation of practices.

synthetic pesticides, such as organic farming or pesticide-free production systems. Adoption can then be defined in a binary way (uptake yes/no). In addition, in these cases, compliance with pesticide use regulations is often controlled by certification and regulatory bodies, which increases data availability and reliability. Integrated or agroecological pest management strategies, on the other hand, are based on recommendations that are not binding and vary between production and environmental contexts. Simple binary indicators of adoption of a practice (from a list of practices) may not be comparable and meaningful across farmers, production systems and cropping seasons. For example, adoption of fewer but more effective practices does not necessarily imply a smaller reduction in pesticide use risks. In this case, one possible approach is to identify common bundles of measures or portfolios ex-post using distance measures (e.g. principal component analysis, see Bailey et al., 2009). This allows identification of bundles of measures across different production contexts, but does not allow assessment of farmer effort or adoption intensity across different production contexts. Furthermore, these adoption indicators are not directly linked to impacts, for example on pesticide risk reduction. A preferred approach would therefore be to use a 'reference framework' (e.g. based on expert opinion) to translate the context-dependent uptake of packages of measures into indicators of adoption intensity, potential pest control efficacy, costs or risk reduction.

Uptake indicators that provide information on the potential risk reduction of pesticides have a more direct policy relevance. Potential risk reduction can be expressed in different units or indicators and in absolute or relative terms compared to a reference period. Importantly, simple indicators of pesticide use (such as number of treatments or kilograms of active ingredient) are often poorly related to pesticide risk reduction. The choice of indicators therefore has important implications for the empirical analysis of farmers' behaviour (Möhring et al., 2019, 2020b, 2023a). To assess the environmental and human health risks of pesticides, pesticide active ingredients can be weighted according to their toxicity using pesticide risk indicators. Two types of risk indicators are relevant: i) indicators that assign specific risk-based weights to each active ingredient used in all contexts, such as the Pesticide Load indicator (Kudsk et al., 2018) or Total Applied Toxicity (Schulz et al., 2021); and ii) indicators of (modelled) risks in environmental compartments that additionally take into account the application context (environmental or application conditions), such as the Risk Score (Tang et al., 2021), the SYNOPSIS indicator (Strassemeyer et al., 2017) and the Environmental Indicator Crop Protection (Focks et al., 2023). The former indicators are less data demanding (requiring only information on the name of the product or active ingredient used), are easily integrated into open-source software (Möhring et al., 2021) and have recently been applied in the literature on farmers' pest management decisions (Jørgensen et al., 2019).

Finally, a potential 'gold standard' for measuring the impact of farmers' crop protection decisions on pesticide risks is the use of single or composite indicators of 'real-time' or ex-post changes in a range of relevant parameters (pollution, ecology, human health). This would imply moving towards outcome and eventually impact based indicators and policies. This does not mean that only one indicator makes sense for policy analysis, but that policy analysis generally should move from simple adoption metrics alone to also consider the potential and realised impacts of adoption. Researchers should therefore always favour indicators with a stronger link to pesticide risk reduction (at the bottom of the table), where data availability allows, and justify their choices.

4. A framework of farmer behaviour for research and policy

This section provides an overview of the determinants that enable or hinder farmers to adopt sustainable crop protection practices. For example, while in section 3 we discussed the challenges of measuring adoption of sustainable crop protection practices, here we focus on what influences and drives farmers' adoption decisions. There are two main

Fig. 1. Framework on Farmer adoption of sustainable crop protection approaches.

elements: First, we develop a general framework for farmers' decisions to adopt sustainable crop protection practices, which provides a holistic view of the factors that influence farmers' decisions. Second, we provide a deeper insight into the behavioural drivers of sustainable crop protection adoption. Based on this section, we: i) identify and structure sources of heterogeneous uptake and adoption of sustainable crop protection approaches across farms, farmers, farming systems and regions, as well as different farmer responses to specific policy incentives, ii) identify leverage points for triggering behaviour change that can complement existing policy instruments, iii) identify gaps and unknowns to guide future research and policy design.

Fig. 1 shows a general framework for farmers' decisions to adopt sustainable crop protection practices. We built on the literature on adoption of new agricultural practices in general (e.g. Pannell et al., 2006, Knowler and Bradshaw, 2007, Prokopy et al., 2008, Baumgart-Getz et al., 2012, Junyu et al., 2022; Kuehne et al., 2017). The framework was also developed based on previous studies in the field of sustainable crop protection, e.g. Lefebvre et al., 2015, Möhring et al., 2020a, Möhring and Finger, 2022. In addition to synthesising existing literature, we used workshops among co-authors to prioritise factors and propose categories.

The framework distinguishes four main categories and their interdependencies. We describe each of these and provide examples of their interdependencies. For example, farmers' risk preferences are more relevant if sustainable crop protection approaches imply higher risks. In addition, the level of compensation from public and market actors required to incentivise behaviour change depends on the economic cost implications of adopting sustainable crop protection practices. While our primary focus is on adoption in general, the timing of adoption and diffusion dynamics are also influenced by the factors presented here in Fig. 1 (e.g. Kuehne et al., 2017).

First, the technical and economic characteristics of sustainable crop protection approaches compared to conventional pest management practices are presented. This includes the cost-effectiveness, technical feasibility, and maturity of alternative strategies, as well as the potential impact on yield quantity and quality as a key measure of their economic viability. This can also be summarised as the relative (dis)advantage of sustainable crop protection strategies (Kuehne et al., 2017). Bremmer et al. (2021) describe a comprehensive overview of alternative

strategies, including technical feasibility and maturity. It also includes impacts on production risks, e.g. non-chemical crop protection may be more risky than chemical crop protection (Möhring et al., 2020b). In addition, the additional costs of replacing pesticides (e.g. increased machinery and labour costs when herbicides are replaced by mechanical weed control, Böcker et al., 2020) can be a barrier to adoption (see Section 2 for detailed insights from examples of herbicide, fungicide and insecticide substitution).

Second, the market environment and input and output prices are important for the adoption of sustainable crop protection approaches. For example, adoption of sustainable crop protection is less likely when pesticides are cheap(er) and alternative strategies (e.g. biological control) are more expensive. Farmers often lack cost-effective substitutes for pesticides, i.e. sustainable crop protection is often unavailable, unknown, too knowledge-intensive and too costly (e.g. Deguine et al., 2021). In addition, sustainable crop protection approaches are more likely to be adopted if such production practices are accepted by downstream actors such as retailers and consumers. For example, fungus-resistant grapevine varieties can significantly reduce dependence on fungicide use, but adoption by farmers will be limited if consumers do not buy wine produced with these varieties, for example because of a different taste (e.g. Finger et al., 2023a). Similarly, fungus-resistant potato varieties reduce dependence on chemical pesticides, but farmers will not grow them if their quality and characteristics do not meet the requirements of downstream actors such as processing industries. Another aspect is the requirements of key value chain partners such as retailers. Consumer concerns mainly relate to the presence of residues in products and their potential toxicological effects. Therefore, retailers have taken on more responsibility and risk in maintaining low pesticide residues and have become more vulnerable and responsive to consumer concerns (Levidov and Bijman, 2002). Low and no pesticide practices can result in price premiums on top of the crop prices for conventional production due to the labelling of sustainable practices (e.g. Crowder and Reganold, 2015; Buurma and Van Der Velden, 2017; Möhring and Finger, 2022). These examples underline that it is crucial to consider the linkages with upstream and downstream actors for farmers' behaviour (e.g. Möhring et al., 2020a).

Third, the policy environment, which includes the regulation of pesticides but also of pesticide alternatives, is important for farmers'

Table 2
Recommendations for uptake indicators of sustainable crop protection.

Type of indicator (main)	Type of indicator (sub)	Direct link to pesticide risk reduction	Recommendation	Data and Method requirements	Typical databases and applications
Adoption intensity	Binary Uptake Indicator	No	For rule-based systems (e.g., organic, pesticide-free).	- Farm-level data on uptake of practice/system (and adoption timing: entry/exit)	- Regional or national farm-level databases - Own survey data
Adoption intensity	Share of adopted practices or bundles (simple count)	No	For systems with a large number of (voluntary) practices changing by context (e.g., IPM) - limited information on actual impact.	- Simple count or share of the number of used practices. - Counting the adoption of groups or bundles of practices (for example grouping of practices using distance measures, such as principal component analysis and cluster analysis, Bailey et al., 2009, Knapp et al., 2019).	- Regional or national farm-level databases - Own survey data
Adoption intensity	Level of adoption (in relation to a reference framework for low- high adoption)	Weak	For systems with a large number of (voluntary) practices changing by context (e.g., IPM) - limited information on actual impact.	- Reference framework to generalise the context-specific data on uptake of (bundles of) measures in (the intensity of) adoption, potential pest control efficacy, or costs. - Data on guidelines by extension services, expert opinions or data from field trials.	- Regional or national farm-level databases - Own survey data
Potential impact of adoption	Change in pesticide use (not weighted for risks).	Weak	For all types of crop protection strategies - does not reflect heterogeneity in potential risks of active ingredients.	- Can be indicators of physical quantities (kilograms per hectare) or monetary indicators (costs per hectare). - Can be numbers of standard dosages, i.e. the applied quantity divided by the maximum allowed application quantity (Treatment Frequency Index).	- Quantity/ monetary indicators widely used in regional or national farm-level databases. - Standard dosage indicators require names and quantities of used products (available in some national databases).
Potential impact of adoption	Change in risk-weighted pesticide use.	Medium	For all types of crop protection strategies.	- Application quantities and/or standard dosages weighted by a risk factor. - The methodology is publicly available and implemented in open-source software (e.g., Möhring et al., 2021; Bub et al., 2022).	- Requires names and quantities of used products. - Access to databases on pesticide properties might be required (available under licence)
Potential impact of adoption	Change in (modelled) environmental impact of crop protection strategies.	Medium	For all types of crop protection strategies.	- (Modelled) persistence in environmental compartments, weighted by a risk factor (e.g., Tang et al., 2021). - Expertise on the modelling of the fate of pesticides in different compartments required. - Exemplary applications are implemented in online platforms (Strassemeyer et al., 2017).	- Requires names and quantities of used products as well as information on the application context (different levels of detail).
Actual impact of adoption	Change in measured (real-time or <i>ex-post</i>) impacts of crop protection strategies.	Strong	For all types of crop protection strategies.	- (real-time) measurement of change in pollution, ecological and human health parameters linked to pesticide use.	Data on pesticide use and risks, (real-time) data on ecological indicators (and human health indicators)

Note: Examples for databases and key references: Regional or national farm-level databases (Region-wide or nationally standardised agricultural data collections, such as the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN), e.g., Uthes et al., 2019, Möhring et al., 2020b), own survey data (cross sectional or panel survey for a specific research project, Knapp et al., 2019, Bakker et al., 2021, Möhring and Finger, 2022).

decisions. For example, stricter pesticide regulations and targeted agri-environmental schemes make sustainable crop protection approaches more attractive to farmers (e.g. Runge et al., 2022). Alternatives to pesticides are also sometimes regulated, e.g. for biological control agents (Van Lenteren, 2001). Policies to support sustainable crop protection can also interact with other dimensions, e.g. taxation of pesticides can increase the cost of pesticides and thus make alternatives more viable for farmers (e.g. Finger et al., 2017), or policies can encourage the development of alternative strategies, e.g. regarding the development of new technologies, farming systems or varieties.

Fourth, farmer-specific behavioural factors (e.g. risk and time preferences, personality and motivations) are important for adoption and are discussed in more detail below.

There are various interactions between the categories shown in Fig. 1. For example, there are interactions between behavioural factors (i.e. network effects) and policy elements (i.e. available information such as extension services), as well as interactions with the market environment (information from private companies). Because of the heterogeneity of all these factors across locations, crops, institutional and market environments, and farmers, as shown in Fig. 1, the adoption

of sustainable crop protection is highly context specific. In addition, sustainable pest management strategies are often more complex and knowledge-intensive than conventional pesticide-based strategies, as they often include a range of preventive measures to suppress pests, as well as direct control methods that need to be adapted to the production environment. Another dimension is the learnability of sustainable crop protection strategies, such as how easy it is for farmers to try, observe and adapt as needed (e.g. Kuehne et al., 2017). An important limitation to the uptake of sustainable crop protection strategies is therefore the lack of knowledge among farmers and extension workers about pest biology and how to apply suppressive methods (Swanton et al., 2008).

4.1. In-depth insights in farmers behavioural factors for research and policy

A wide range of behavioural factors play a role in the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices. In this subsection, we examine the main behavioural factors that influence the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices. To do so, we have classified the factors into categories based on the studies by Dessart et al. (2019), Schaub et al. (2023)

and Wuepper et al. (2023b), but frame and discuss them in the context of sustainable crop protection. In Table 3, we describe for each of these categories how they affect adoption, with some examples and key literature. We also identify gaps and open questions that require further research in this area.

4.2. Economic preferences

A key economic consideration in encouraging farmers to adopt sustainable crop protection is its economic viability (and the net benefits of adoption), taking into account changes in costs and benefits. Specifically, farmers will typically not adopt new practices if it means losing money (Finger and Möhring, 2024). However, more than the expected value of the net benefits of adoption is important in explaining farmers' adoption behaviour; for example, risk perceptions may play an important role. How farmers deal with risk over time can be very different and depends on their preferences. Farmers face different sources of risk and uncertainty in their farming activities, ranging from changes in weather, pests, diseases, markets, policies and institutions. For example, crop protection decisions are made under considerable uncertainty about future pest occurrence and pressure, and about the effectiveness of pest control measures. Farmers' risk preferences therefore play an important role in sustainable crop protection decision-making.

On average, farmers are risk averse, preferring certainty to uncertainty (e.g. Iyer et al., 2020). Higher risk aversion is often associated with higher pesticide use and lower adoption of sustainable crop protection practices (see Table 3). However, risk aversion is not a simple measure or concept. For example, behavioural decision research has shown that risk attitudes can vary across different decision domains and different theoretical concepts are used (e.g. Finger et al., 2024b). For example, farmers may be averse to environmental and health risks but risk-seeking for production risks, and risk preferences in each domain may have different implications for pest management decisions (Finger et al., 2023b; Iyer et al., 2020; Garcia et al., 2024). In addition to risk preferences, it is important to examine risk perceptions, that is, how farmers assess the probabilities and outcomes of uncertain events (e.g. Babcock, 2015). In general, as with other sustainable practices, the higher the perceived risk associated with more sustainable crop protection practices, the lower the adoption (Möhring et al., 2023b).

Time preferences refer to how farmers value the present versus the future. Farmers tend to be impatient (Wuepper et al., 2023c). Although time preferences are relevant to farmer behaviour (e.g. Sarwosri and Mußhoff, 2020), they are often overlooked in the literature on adoption of sustainable crop protection practices. However, time preferences can help us understand why farmers may be reluctant to adopt such practices (Table 3). For example, some of the benefits of sustainable crop management practices, such as improved soil health, may only be realised in the long term and may not benefit the current generation of farmers, or their benefits may be strongly discounted by farmers (e.g. Wuepper et al., 2023c).

4.3. Motivations, abilities, and individual differences

To understand why farmer choose certain practices, it is important to recognise that not all motivations are captured by economic preferences. Some motivations may stem from obligations, duties or norms (e.g. Engelen, 2017). If farmers differ in their intrinsic and extrinsic motivations, this implies that a one-size-fits-all approach to helping farmers adopt sustainable pest management practices will not be effective. In research on farmer behaviour based on motivations, it has been suggested to conceptualise behaviour change as a transition through a temporal sequence of different stages (Bamberg, 2013; Wang et al., 2023a), or different stages (e.g. pre-decision vs. pre-action stage) require different interventions. From this perspective, the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices should first and foremost be in line with farmers' objectives (Table 3).

Table 3

In-depth insights on behavioural factors for assessing farmers' adoption of sustainable crop protection practices.

Categories of Behavioural Factors	Main directions and mechanisms observed in the literature	References/ Examples	Gaps and open issues
Risk preferences	Risk preferences are attitudes towards risky and uncertain outcomes or situations. More risk averse farmers are less likely to adopt sustainable crop protection practices than risk neutral farmers. They prefer to avoid or minimise (financial) risk and choose safer options with lower but more certain payoffs.	Wang and Finger (2023) show that risk averse farmers are less likely to use preventive measures. Garcia et al. (2024) show that higher risk aversion reduces the adoption of pesticide-free production. Björnåvold et al. (2022) show that farmers cannot foresee what a pesticide-free future would look like due to a variety of technological, economic, social and political uncertainties.	It is important to distinguish between the impact of measures on farmers' economic risk in a given system and farmers' uncertainty about adopting a new system with unknown costs and benefits. The risk effects of sustainable crop protection may differ between domains, e.g. increasing yield risk but reducing environmental and health risk. Therefore, domain-specific assessments of risk and risk preferences are needed. However, the impact of risk is very context specific. Pannell (1991) shows that the influence of risk aversion on decisions about pesticide use rates can go either way, depending on the magnitude of the risk for different variables that affect the overall risk in different ways.
Risk perceptions	Risk perceptions include individuals' cognitive and subjective evaluations of the potential harm or likelihood of loss. The higher the perceived production, market and political risk associated with sustainable crop protection practices, the lower the uptake.	Garcia et al. (2024) show that farmers who perceive higher production, market and political risks associated with pesticide-free production are less likely to adopt it. Möhring et al. (2023b) show that the difference between modelled ("objective") and perceived yield and risk effects is particularly important for the adoption of pesticide-free wheat production.	Background risks (such as general political and market risks) influence farmers' sustainable crop protection decisions. However, the perception of these background risks and their interaction with foreground risks (e.g. yield risk) is often not considered. It is important to explore how farmers perceive and respond to different types and areas of risk. Farmers are often more averse to uncertainty than to risk, i.e. when they do not have enough information and experience (e.g. with sustainable

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Categories of Behavioural Factors	Main directions and mechanisms observed in the literature	References/ Examples	Gaps and open issues
Time preferences	Time preferences capture the extent to which current monetary outcomes are valued over future monetary outcomes using discount rates. Farmers with higher time discount rates (less patient) are less likely to adopt sustainable crop protection practices than farmers with lower time discount rates (more patient).	Sun et al. (2017) found that farmers may choose not to use different sustainable measures to reduce the risk of herbicide-resistant weeds because the benefits are delayed (and uncertain), while the costs are immediate and certain. The additional time required to use more diversified measures may discourage the adoption of reduced herbicide use.	crop protection) to form subjective probabilities. However, these uncertainty perceptions (and preferences) are rarely taken into account. Sustainable crop protection practices aim at long-term soil and ecosystem health, while time preferences may be influenced by, for example, age, income, expected needs, etc. It is not clear which source of uncertainty is the main driver of farmers' sustainable crop protection decisions and trade-offs over time.
Heuristics and cognitive biases	While some farmers may base their decisions on careful analysis and comparison of different options, others may rely on intuitive and habitual processes that operate automatically and unconsciously (see Dual System Theory). The willingness to adopt sustainable crop protection practices can also be influenced by automatic decision-making processes.	Buchholz and Musshoff (2021) compare the impact of a pesticide tax and a green nudge on the treatment frequency index of pesticide use in a business game with German farmers and find that both reduce pesticide use (measured as the treatment frequency index), i. e. the tax by 14% and the nudge by 6%. Zachmann et al. (2023) use a randomised experiment to test whether providing farmers with personalised or general information on the use of environmentally toxic fungicides changes their intentions to adopt fungus-resistant varieties (i.e. salience nudging). They find no effect of either personalised or general information.	An open question is whether interventions targeting automatic processes lead to lasting changes in farmers' adoption behaviour and attitudes towards sustainable pest management practices, or whether they are only temporary. More research is needed on the contexts and scenarios in which nudges outperform (are more effective) or complement neoclassical instruments (extrinsic).
Social capital and culture	Social capital refers to the factors embedded in social networks,	Wang et al. (2023b) show the importance of spillover effects in	Social and peer effects have mainly been studied using cross-sectional data.

Table 3 (continued)

Categories of Behavioural Factors	Main directions and mechanisms observed in the literature	References/ Examples	Gaps and open issues
	such as norms, values and trust. Culture shapes these factors. Social capital can facilitate cooperation and coordination among farmers in adopting sustainable crop protection practices. Extension and information channels play an important role here, but how exactly is complex to predict and context-dependent.	farmers' decisions to adopt pesticide-free crop production. They also highlight the importance of accounting for potentially heterogeneous social ties in farmer networks, beyond pure measures of spatial proximity. Läßle and Kelley (2015) analyse spatial dependence in the adoption of organic farming, finding that farmers in close proximity show similar selection behaviour. Foolen-Torgerson et al. (2023) explored how group discussions influence farmers' decision-making processes regarding crop and soil health. They found that group discussions helped farmers to increase their awareness and understanding and to overcome the limitations of individual judgement and technical expertise.	Dynamic analyses that take into account the temporal aspects of these effects are lacking. Social and peer effects can interact with policy measures. However, this interaction is rarely considered in the context of sustainable crop protection. Farmers' preferences for extension and information attributes have rarely been assessed in the context of sustainable crop protection. Social capital can strongly influence the implementation of sustainable crop protection at different scales, for example at the landscape level, where interaction and cooperation are required. However, it should be noted that while it can help facilitate adoption, it is not effective and efficient on its own. It can therefore complement other measures and be part of a useful policy mix. More research is needed on how the diffusion of sustainable crop protection innovations works, and how to reach different farmer adopter segments.
Personality and individual differences	Personality and individual differences refer to the traits or characteristics that distinguish people from one another. Cognitive skills refer to the mental processes for acquiring, processing and using information for reasoning and problem solving. Non-cognitive skills refer to a range of personal qualities, habits and general attitudes that influence how, for example, farmers approach tasks and deal with different	Barham et al. (2018) showed, in the context of adoption of genetically modified maize seeds, that early adopters are those who score high on cognitive ability and are not receptive to advice. Barton et al. (1990) examined the relationship between personality and farmers' use of IPM practices. They found that certain personality variables were good predictors of adoption. Austin et al. (2001) found that farmers who scored high on	As suggested by Buurma and Van Der Velden (2017), aligning differences in farmers' cognitive and non-cognitive skills (e.g. by entrepreneurial type) with the policy and market environment is crucial to provide the right incentives for the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices.

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Categories of Behavioural Factors	Main directions and mechanisms observed in the literature	References/ Examples	Gaps and open issues
	situations. How cognitive and non-cognitive skills and personality affect the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices is complex to predict and context-dependent.	cognitive ability, assertiveness and openness to new experiences were more likely to adopt environmentally friendly practices. They also argue that this type of association is influenced by participants' attitudes towards achieving goals in farming, their views on the use of chemicals in farming, and their goals to explore activities beyond farming.	
Motivations to engage in voluntary behaviour	Understanding why people engage in voluntary behaviour requires an analysis of their motivations. Motivations can be classified as intrinsic or extrinsic; they can arise from personal (self-) interest and satisfaction or from external rewards and pressures. The higher the motivation, the more likely it is that sustainable crop protection practices will be adopted.	Bopp et al. (2019) find that when adopting sustainable agricultural practices, farmers with high intrinsic motivation are not influenced by the presence of external incentives. Bakker et al. (2021) show that the intention to reduce pesticide use is driven by attitudes and subjective norms (especially descriptive norms), and that farmers need successful examples through peer exchange or knowledge provision. Finger and Möhring (2022) show that farmers who perceive higher environmental and human health benefits from low pesticide practices are more likely to adopt these practices. Knapp et al. (2021) find that adoption of preventive measures against pests is associated with higher internal locus of control and higher aspirations. Bijttebier et al. (2018) show that the main motivators and barriers to the adoption of non-inversion tillage across Europe are region and context	More nuanced measurements of the adoption process can be taken in motivational studies, e.g. by understanding and measuring adoption as a sequence of stages. This also applies to the notion of bundles or portfolios when measuring adoption. Researchers should compare 'rational' (e.g. profit or utility maximising) and observed behaviour in recommendation-based pest management systems such as IPM.
Perceived ability to perform a behaviour	Perceived behavioural control refers to the extent to which people believe they have the ability (more internal) and/or the resources (more external) to perform a particular behaviour. It can also include the expectation of controllability, i.e.	Knapp et al. (2021) find that adoption of preventive measures against pests is associated with higher internal locus of control and higher aspirations. Bijttebier et al. (2018) show that the main motivators and barriers to the adoption of non-inversion tillage across Europe are region and context	There is a lack of attention to the role of contextual factors in farmers' motivation and ability to adopt sustainable crop protection practices. Examples of such contextual factors include age, education and dependence on farm income. This type of analysis has mostly been

Table 3 (continued)

Categories of Behavioural Factors	Main directions and mechanisms observed in the literature	References/ Examples	Gaps and open issues
	that it is not up to them to perform the behaviour. It includes the constructs of self-efficacy and locus of control. The higher the perceived ability, the more likely it is that sustainable crop protection practices will be adopted.	specific, and partly explained by institutional and cultural conditions.	studied using cross-sectional data. Dynamic analyses that take into account the spatial and temporal aspects of these effects are lacking.

In addition to the motivation to adopt sustainable crop protection practices, farmers need certain skills, knowledge, and cooperation with other people to implement these practices effectively (Bakker et al., 2021). To implement sustainable crop protection practices efficiently and effectively at different levels (from fields to farms to landscapes), social interactions and relationships that foster cooperation and coordination between farmers and other stakeholders are essential. Farmers may face various barriers to adoption, such as lack of money, time or other resources. These factors influence farmers' perceived behavioural control, self-efficacy and locus of control, which are interrelated and may reflect both internal and external control factors (Ajzen, 2002). Differences in personality and cognitions may explain why farmers perceive their ability (e.g. to effectively control pests) differently and thus choose specific pest management strategies (Knapp et al., 2021). These differences also explain why innovators and early adopters are less likely to use advisory information sources and adopt immediately without waiting to see what their peers do (Läpple and Van Rensburg, 2011; Barham et al., 2018; Maertens, 2017).

To reach adopter segments other than innovators or early adopters, social networks are crucial to facilitate cooperation and coordination among farmers in adopting sustainable crop protection practices.⁹ However, social networks can also have a negative effect in some cultural contexts if they make farmers resistant to new technologies or practices due to a preference for traditional methods, which in our context means relying mainly on pesticide use (Wuepper et al., 2023a). The channels through which information flows to farmers are also important, e.g. whether extension services are public or private (Polman and Slangen, 2008; Peerlings and Polman, 2009; Wuepper et al., 2021).

4.4. Policy implications related to farmer behavioural factors

From a policy perspective, the categories presented in Table 3 are relevant for understanding how the effectiveness of policy instruments to change behaviour is influenced by these behavioural factors (see also Kvakkestad et al., 2021; Möhring et al., 2020a). It is also important to emphasise that these identified categories of behavioural factors for the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices interact as interdependencies with the other categories (i.e. technical and economic characteristics, policy environment and market environment) of the framework presented in Fig. 1. For example, matching differences in farmers' cognitive and non-cognitive abilities (e.g. by entrepreneurial type) with the policy and market environment is critical to providing the

⁹ It should be noted, however, that not all farmers can be reached through social networks. For example, Wang et al. (2023b) find that the spillover effects of pesticide use are only robust for farmers who also consult peers on agricultural decisions.

right incentives for the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices.

Thus, the risk and time dimensions of sustainable crop protection practices are crucial for understanding how farmers can be incentivised to adopt sustainable crop protection practices in heterogeneous policy and market environments. Reducing the increased financial risk to farmers of switching to low pesticide strategies may be a viable way to facilitate the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices. Particularly for practices aimed at redesigning farming systems with long time horizons and large uncertainties, research and policy need to provide not only risk management tools, but also “time management tools”. These tools need to take into account how changing economic and social conditions in agriculture affect the adoption of sustainable crop protection in the short and long term.

In addition, a combination of instruments is best used in a synergistic way to promote the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices. In addition to information and incentive-based instruments, our review suggests that nudges (e.g. based on social norms) can act as catalysts for the diffusion of these practices. Thus, in addition to policy instruments that rely on deliberative and self-regulatory processes, there are tools (based on nudges) that target automatic processes in decision-making, such as heuristics, biases and emotions (e.g. Byerly et al., 2018; Balmford et al., 2021). For example, in crop protection systems that rely on contextual recommendations, such as IPM, a utility maximising farmer might not actually reduce pesticide use if it is not beneficial and strictly necessary. However, such decisions may not be similar for all farmers, but may be strongly influenced by individual (behavioural) factors, leaving room for optimising tools and programmes. More research is needed to inform policymaking on whether and how nudges can be used to change farmers’ behaviour towards sustainable crop management practices. However, nudges often have very small effects (e.g. Howley and Ocean, 2022), but are cheap to implement. They can therefore play a role in complementing other policy instruments, but cannot fully replace other measures.

5. Methods to assess farmer behaviour towards sustainable crop protection approaches in research and policy analysis

In this section, we aim to draw out the implications of the findings in the previous sections for the methods used to study farmers’ decisions to adopt sustainable crop management practices, to assess their impacts, and to evaluate policies. In doing so, we aim to improve the methodological basis for research and policy decisions. We focus on two key aspects identified above, for both ex-ante and ex-post analyses (e.g. El Benni et al., 2023). First, how sustainable crop protection approaches are defined and how is adoption measured (sections 2 & 3). Second, what are the determinants, and in particular behavioural factors, that are relevant for farmers’ decisions to adopt sustainable crop protection practices (section 4).

5.1. Ex-ante and ex-post assessments to study sustainable crop protection

In ex-ante analyses, the adoption of sustainable crop protection is studied before policies and new pest management measures (e.g. new varieties and new technologies) are introduced, i.e. the focus is on potential and expected decisions. A wide range of methodological approaches are used to study ex-ante farmer behaviour, ranging from simulation and optimisation models to experimental and qualitative approaches. The choice of methods is crucial for the policy context.

Ex-ante evaluations often rely on farm-level bio-economic models, sector models and agent-based simulation and optimisation models (e.g. Mack et al., 2023; Jacquet et al., 2011). These models assume goal functions for farmers (e.g. profit or utility maximisation) and take into account various constraints on farmers’ decision making. Thus, they allow for changes in farmers’ behaviour under different policy, market and environmental conditions. Assessing the adoption of bundles of sustainable crop protection practices and their impacts requires a

detailed consideration of pesticide use and its alternatives. In addition to simulation and optimisation models, surveys and, increasingly, experimental approaches are used in ex-ante analyses to investigate the potential effects of policies. These approaches allow researchers to consider and directly elicit farmers’ behaviour, rather than assuming farmers’ objective functions and decisions. Ex-ante survey approaches are based, for example, on the Theory of Planned Behaviour framework (Sok et al., 2021; Bakker et al., 2021) or a discrete choice experimental approach (e.g. Chèze et al., 2020). Experimental approaches focus on randomly assigning a sub-sample of farmers to a treatment (e.g. a new policy or a new pest management technology) or a control group. Farmers then make decisions that reveal their response to the treatment (e.g. Danne et al., 2019; Zachmann et al., 2023).¹⁰

Ex-post analyses examine farmers’ actual decisions to adopt sustainable pest management practices, e.g. in response to a policy. These analyses are often based on econometric approaches that exploit the temporal and spatial heterogeneity of farmers’ pest management decisions, e.g. derived from farm accountancy data and census data (e.g. Jacquet et al., 2011). Survey data in ex-post analyses are used to collect additional information, such as farmers’ actual pest management practices (e.g. Creissen et al., 2019; Möhring and Finger, 2022). An important aspect enabled by ex-post analysis is the identification of causal relationships between a treatment (e.g. a new policy) and realised outcomes (e.g. a change in farmers’ behaviour), for example by using non-random treatments in quasi-experimental situations (e.g. Wuepper and Finger, 2023). In addition, where data on the adoption and impact of new systems or technologies are lacking, as is particularly the case for crop protection (Mesnage et al., 2021), expert judgements could be used to gather data on potential impacts. These could be used in combination with external data to assess (potential) impacts econometrically or through modelling (Möhring et al., 2024; Mack et al., 2023).

Qualitative approaches, such as interviews and focus groups, can also be used to investigate actual decisions and their underlying determinants, as well as potential changes in farmer behaviour (Fig. 2). Thus, qualitative approaches can contribute to both ex-ante and ex-post policy evaluations and allow for in-depth assessments of farmer behaviour.

5.2. Lack of refined definitions of sustainable crop protection in ex-ante and ex-post assessments

Current ex-ante and ex-post methodological approaches used to assess farmers’ behaviour towards sustainable crop protection practices and policy analysis (Fig. 2) still rarely take into account how sustainable crop protection practices are defined and how adoption and impacts are measured (Sections 2 & 3). Assessing the adoption of packages of sustainable crop protection measures and their impacts, for example on pesticide risk reduction, requires detailed consideration and analysis of pesticide use and other crop protection measures, often through interdisciplinary collaboration. In this sense, assessing the potential impacts of adopting sustainable crop protection requires detailed information on pesticide use and its potential substitutes, as well as their impacts on target indicators under different environmental conditions. For example, Böcker et al. (2019, 2020) provide an ex-ante analysis for the adoption of non-chemical weed control as well as a detailed description of herbicide use. Based on this, they assess the impact of reduced pesticide use using the Danish Pesticide Load indicator of potential pesticide risks (Kudsk et al., 2018). However, this level of detail used in Böcker et al. (2019, 2020) is missing in currently used farm and sector level models (see Dueri and Mack, 2024 for an exception). Thus, the systematic incorporation of details of pest management practices and

¹⁰ See also Kuehne et al. (2017) for a tool (ADOPT) for predicting the uptake of new agricultural practices ex ante, based on a framework and expert knowledge that can be easily applied by practitioners in research, extension and policy.

Fig. 2. Methodological Approaches to assess Sustainable Crop Protection Practices and Related Policies in the Policy Cycle.

their potential impacts on human health and the environment is a key task for research to provide meaningful policy analysis. However, the complexity of farm-level pest management may require a simplified representation of sustainable crop protection approaches, especially in large-scale optimisation and simulation models (e.g. Mack et al., 2023). In the same vein, the complexity of farm-level pest management and its implications are not usually reflected in economic experiments used for ex-ante evaluation, such as choice experiments. These often focus on individual measures and do not consider the impact dimensions (e.g. Table 2) (e.g. Chèze et al., 2020, Danne & Musshoff 2019, Zachmann et al., 2023).

Similarly, ex-post analyses of sustainable crop protection practices and related policies typically lack details on pesticide use and impacts. For example, detailed information on pesticide use (e.g. active ingredients, quantity, timing and method of application) is not included in widely used databases for European agriculture, such as the Farm Accountancy Data Network and census data (Mesnage et al., 2021). Therefore, filling data gaps will be a key requirement for improving methods for policy analysis to the required level. The limitations of current methodological approaches are even more pronounced for adoption impacts that require the measurement of ecological (e.g. biodiversity, water pollution) and human health impacts, i.e. the lack of data is even more pronounced. However, there are several ways forward. For example, details on pest management practices and pesticide use can increasingly be collected through farmer surveys (see e.g. Zachmann et al., 2023), but this usually requires a lot of time and resources and is subject to potential measurement errors. A viable complementary strategy is therefore to expand the documentation of pest management practices in standardised data collections, such as the Farm Accountancy Data Network and census data collection. Currently, data on pesticide use are only available systematically (for all farms, over several years) in a few regions worldwide, e.g. in Denmark and California (e.g. Kudsk et al., 2018; Larsen et al., 2017). The EU is planning to develop a Farm Sustainability Data Network, which will include such information and may therefore be essential for improving future policy analysis (Vrolijk and Poppe, 2021). In this sense, the more widespread use of digital technologies will also mean that more details of pest management practices and pesticide use could be documented (Finger, 2023).

A further combination of qualitative and quantitative data and methods may also be required to better capture the details of sustainable crop protection and its impacts (e.g. Weltin et al., 2021). For example, extension service guidelines, expert opinions or data from field trials or previous farm-level econometric analyses can serve as a reference for transforming data and assumptions. Such reference frameworks can be integrated directly in ex-post studies, but also in ex-ante studies, such as

surveys of planned behaviour (e.g. Bakker et al., 2021), discrete choice experiments (e.g. Chèze et al., 2020) or bio-economic models (e.g. Mack et al., 2023), to better measure the potential impact of the (hypothetical) behavioural changes under consideration.

To enable the measurement and identification of the actual impacts of the adoption of sustainable crop protection and policy impacts, information on a range of relevant categories (economic, environmental, human health) needs to be monitored. Such arrangements for assessing the actual impacts of farmers' crop protection decisions have also been proposed in the context of a review of current environmental risk assessments of pesticides (Milner and Boyd, 2017; Topping et al., 2020). This usually requires long-term, transdisciplinary research platforms such as on-farm experiments and living laboratories (Lacoste et al., 2022). Several examples of such research platforms exist, for example at a regional scale in France (Gaba and Bretagnolle, 2020) and at a larger scale in China (Cui et al., 2018). The current lack of such assessments calls for more ex-post analyses that examine real-world impacts, for example on water pollution or biodiversity, after new measures and/or policies have been implemented. Such evaluations can also be integrated into ex-ante evaluations based on experiments. For example, randomised control trials, which take into account actual outcomes and impacts as well as the underlying mechanisms, can increasingly be used for ex-ante assessment of real-world impacts, e.g. where only a smaller area, such as a specific region, is used to test policies. In addition, improved data on detailed pest management practices that are available over time and space will allow us to identify the causal effects of adopting sustainable crop protection on the environment and human health (e.g. Larsen et al., 2017).

5.3. Lack of consideration of behavioural factors in ex-ante and ex-post assessments

The methodological approaches currently used to assess farmer behaviour towards sustainable crop protection approaches and policy analysis (Fig. 2) lack consideration of the behavioural factors identified in Section 4.2. For example, risk and time preferences, personality and social networks are usually not considered in ex-ante farm-level modelling approaches (see e.g. Reidsma et al., 2018; Huber et al., 2022), despite their potential importance for farmers' adoption decisions towards sustainable crop protection approaches. The consideration of a wide range of behavioural factors in ex-post analyses of sustainable crop protection is also not widely developed (e.g. Möhring et al., 2020a; Knapp et al., 2021). For example, behavioural factors are not documented in databases such as the Farm Accountancy Data Network and are rarely considered in primary data collection in surveys. An important challenge will be to link these databases to (proxies for) farmer

behaviour at a larger scale, as they often only contain information on farm and farmer characteristics. Eliciting the full range of preferences, perceptions, personality and networks mentioned above in surveys, experiments and interviews is usually difficult, e.g. due to time constraints. Therefore, the integration of behavioural aspects into databases and farmer surveys will require addressing trade-offs between the detail and depth of elicitation tasks and the time available for surveys and experiments. To this end, less time-consuming elicitation tasks can be used. For example, by using self-assessment of risk and time preferences instead of incentivised tasks such as lotteries (cf. Iyer et al., 2020; Wuepper et al., 2023c). In addition, different data sources can be combined to avoid duplication of data collection and to make surveys more efficient. For example, separate surveys to measure behavioural factors can be combined with other databases. However, this raises major privacy issues. For ex-ante modelling approaches, taking these aspects into account will require fundamental adjustments, e.g. in the assumed target functions. In particular, it is necessary to go beyond profit maximisation and integrate concepts such as time and risk preferences, perceptual biases, personality and networks. To this end, surveys, i.e. the elicitation of farmers' preferences and the empirical analysis of their networks, need to be combined with farm-level and agent-based modelling approaches (see e.g. Huber et al., 2023 and Kreft et al., 2023 for examples). The methods used must also be appropriate to the nature of the policy. For example, incorporating policies such as nudges requires different methodological approaches than investigating the potential effects of a subsidy or price premium. For example, standard objective functions such as profit or expected utility maximisation may not reflect the effects of nudges; a choice experiment may be more appropriate.

5.4. System perspectives are required

Reducing the risk of pesticide use requires a holistic systems perspective and must go beyond farm level considerations. While our analysis focused mainly on the farm level, the agri-food system perspective is key for such a transition to sustainable crop protection, as many of the drivers of farmers' decisions discussed here are set and influenced by other food system actors (e.g. Möhring et al., 2020a; Oude Lansink et al., 2018; Rodenburg et al., 2015; Schut et al., 2014). Effective and efficient policies need to include all actors in the food value chain, i.e. from upstream companies, farmers, downstream industries to consumers (Möhring et al., 2020a). For example, acceptance and support of low pesticide production systems can facilitate a large-scale transition (e.g. Finger and Möhring, 2024). The required holistic systems perspective should therefore be based on insights from individual actor behaviour, but also from policymakers who shape regulations, innovators who create new technologies, retailers and industry who create new products and labels, and consumers who make purchasing decisions. Farmers' behaviour in these production systems is interdependent and influenced by various factors such as individual beliefs, incentives, societal norms and organisational structures, which also feedback on each other (e.g. Engler et al., 2019). Furthermore, barriers to innovation adoption can be influenced by both individual and systemic factors (Kuntosch and König, 2018). Thus, from a policy perspective, it is important to understand and steer individual behaviour, taking into account key actors and actions at the food system level.

6. Conclusion and implications for policy and research

In this paper, we have provided insights into the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices in European agriculture. We used an interdisciplinary perspective, combining agronomic insights into farming practices, aspects underlying farmer behaviour to adopt these practices, and the methodologies used to study farmer behaviour and assess potential policy impacts. We identified the following key issues. First, sustainable crop protection practices consist of combinations and

bundles of individual measures, which are not currently considered on a regular basis. Second, current definitions of adoption and measures of policy success often focus on simple adoption measures. Third, we show that farmers' adoption decisions are based on a wide range of determinants, but in particular the consideration of behavioural factors is potentially highly relevant but currently underexplored. Fourth, the tools used for policy analysis do not allow for the representation of key aspects identified in our analysis, e.g. focusing on the impact of pest management practices and policies as well as on factors underlying farmer behaviour.

6.1. Implications for policy

First, policies must focus on the impacts (e.g. on the environment and human health) of sustainable crop protection practices and policies that support their adoption. This implies that measures of policy success need to move away from simple adoption metrics alone (measure adopted or not) to consider the impacts of adoption, for example on pesticide risk reduction. Second, policy measures need to take into account the great importance of behavioural factors underlying farmers' decisions to adopt sustainable crop protection practices (and to what extent). This opens up new avenues for policy instruments, i.e. going beyond command and control measures (e.g. banning pesticides and regulating their use) and economic instruments (e.g. subsidies and taxes). For example, we identified risks as a key factor limiting the adoption of sustainable crop protection practices, and thus policy can carefully provide farmers with tools to reduce these risks associated with sustainable crop protection. Furthermore, our finding on the relevance of social and spill-over effects, especially for policies and practices at the landscape level, means that policies should aim to use farmer-farmer interaction and policies that support it as a viable way to promote the use of sustainable crop protection practices. The relevance of information and framing can open avenues for the use of instruments such as nudges in the policy toolbox. Third, better databases are needed. To enable evidence-based policy making, we need better and more detailed data on pest management practices and pesticide use. Monitoring of relevant outcomes also needs to be strengthened. Fourth, evidence-based policy needs to be based on state-of-the-art methods for ex-ante and ex-post evaluation. These tools are currently missing from the standard toolbox, so investment in their development may be worthwhile.

6.2. Implications for research

First, we need to broaden our focus on the adoption of pest management practices. Instead of focusing on specific (individual) concepts, measures and practices, a more holistic focus on a wide range of strategies and bundles of measures in the context of sustainable pest management practices is needed. This implies more sophisticated strategies for representing pest management in farm-level, agent-based and sectoral models as well as in data collection efforts. In addition, we need to shift our attention to the impact of farmer behaviour, using indicators that are better aligned with actual policy objectives. Second, we need to rethink farmer behaviour in the context of sustainable crop protection practices. A wide range of behavioural factors need to be taken into account that are so far underexplored and not well enough understood. Third, new methodological developments are needed to address these issues. Current tools for assessing farmer behaviour and policy are not well suited to assessing pesticide policies. For example, models often fail to take account of behavioural factors and cannot represent environmental and human health impacts. We have shown here that it is not enough to adopt approaches from other research questions and use them for sustainable adoption of pesticides, but that there are specific challenges and contexts that need to be considered when analysing farmers' adoption decisions. Enabling these developments will require a creative combination of methods and data in an interdisciplinary setting, e.g. combining economic, agronomic and ecological research to provide, for

example, reference frameworks for the adoption of sustainable crop protection and its impacts. To enable the above developments, it will also be necessary to combine ex-post and ex-ante approaches (e.g. integrating surveys and network analysis in farm-level and agent-based models). In this sense, the increased use and integration of economic experiments to study farmer behaviour in the context of sustainable pest management practices is promising. Fourth, the introduction of new policy instruments discussed above (e.g. risk-based, network-based, nudges) also requires research in these areas to provide insights for evidence-based policy making.

The conceptual framework presented in Fig. 1 also points to the importance of study design, particularly in ex-post studies. The conceptual framework includes factors at the individual level (explaining, for example, why different farmers in the same region, sector and value chain might still differ in terms of adoption and adoption intensity), at the meso level (explaining, for example, why farmers in the same region and sector and with similar farming behaviours but in different value chains might differ in terms of adoption and adoption intensity) and at the macro level (explaining, for example, why overall adoption and adoption intensity is higher in one sector or region than in another). In order to investigate the impact of these factors holistically in an ex-post setting, a multi-stage study design may be required that takes these different levels into account. Standardisation of study designs will further increase the comparability of studies across regions and production systems and allow for meta-analyses across different levels.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Robert Finger: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Jaap Sok:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Emmanuel Ahovi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Sharmin Akter:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Johan Bremmer:** Writing – review & editing. **Silke Dachbrodt-Saaydeh:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Carolien de Lauwere:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Cordelia Kreft:** Writing – original draft. **Per Kudsk:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Fatima Lambarraa-Lehnhardt:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Chloe McCallum:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Alfons Oude Lansink:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Erwin Wauters:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft. **Niklas Möhring:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

None.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Acknowledgment

This research was carried out as part of the project SUPPORT Supporting Uptake Integrated Pest Management and Low-Risk Pesticide Use, funded by the European Union's (EU) Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101084527, <https://he-support.eu/>. The content of this article does not represent the official position of the European Union. The information and views expressed are the sole responsibility of the authors. We thank the participants of the organised session on 'Economics and Policy of Integrated Pest Management' at the XVII EAAE Congress for fruitful discussions. We thank the editor and a reviewer for very helpful feedback and suggestions.

References

- Adeux, G., Vieren, E., Carlesi, S., Bärberi, P., Munier-Jolain, N., Cordeau, S., 2019. Mitigating crop yield losses through weed diversity. *Nature Sustainability* 2 (11), 1018–1026.
- Ajzen, I., 2002. Perceived behavioral control, self-efficacy, locus of control, and the theory of planned behavior. *J. Appl. Soc. Psychol.* 32, 665–683.
- Akhter, M.J., Sønderkov, M., Lodd, D., Ulber, L., Hull, R., Kudsk, P., 2023. Opportunities and challenges for harvest weed seed control in European cropping systems. *Eur. J. Agron.* 142, 126639. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2022.126639>.
- Austin, C., Arcury, T.A., Quandt, S.A., Preisser, J.S., Saavedra, R.M., Cabrera, L.F., 2001. Training farmworkers about pesticide safety: issues of control. *J. Health Care Poor Underserved* 12 (2), 236–249.
- Babcock, B.A., 2015. Using cumulative Prospect theory to explain anomalous crop insurance coverage choice. *Am. J. Agric. Econ.* 97, 1371–1384.
- Bailey, A.S., Bertaglia, M., Fraser, I.M., Sharma, A., Douarin, E., 2009. Integrated pest management portfolios in UK arable farming: results of a farmer survey. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 65 (9), 1030–1039.
- Bakker, L., Sok, J., Van Der Werf, W., Bianchi, F.J.J.A., 2021. Kicking the habit: what makes and breaks farmers' intentions to reduce pesticide use? *Ecol. Econ.* 180, 106868.
- Balmford, A., Bradbury, R.B., Bauer, J.M., Broad, S., Burgess, G., Burgman, M., Byerly, H., Clayton, S., Espeloin, D., Ferraro, P., Fisher, B., Garnett, E.E., 2021. Making more effective use of human behavioural science in conservation interventions. *Biol. Conserv.* 261, 109256.
- Bamberg, S., 2013. Changing environmentally harmful behaviors: a stage model of self-regulated behavioral change. *J. Environ. Psychol.* 34, 151–159.
- Barham, B.L., Chavas, J.P., Fitz, D., Schechter, L., 2018. Receptiveness to advice, cognitive ability, and technology adoption. *J. Econ. Behav. Organ.* 149, 239–268.
- Barton, K., Grieshop, J.L., Miyao, G., Zalom, F.G., 1990. Farmers' personality related to implementation of integrated pest management. *Knowledge* 12, 3–13.
- Barzman, M., Bärberi, P., Birch, A.N.E., Boonekamp, P., Dachbrodt-Saaydeh, S., Graf, B., Sattin, M., 2015. Eight principles of integrated pest management. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 35, 1199–1215.
- Baumgart-Getz, A., Stalker Prokopy, L., Floress, K., 2012. Why farmers adopt best management practice in the United States: a meta-analysis of the adoption literature. *J. Environ. Manag.* 96 (1), 17–25.
- Bijttebier, J., Ruyschaert, G., Hijbeek, R., Werner, M., Pronk, A.A., Zavattaro, L., Bechini, L., Grignani, C., ten Berge, H., Marchand, F., Wauters, E., 2018. Adoption of non-inversion tillage across Europe: use of a behavioural approach in understanding decision making of farmers. *Land Use Policy* 78, 460–471.
- Bjørnåvold, A., David, M., Bohan, D.A., Gibert, C., Rousselle, J.M., Van Passel, S., 2022. Why does France not meet its pesticide reduction targets? Farmers' socio-economic trade-offs when adopting agro-ecological practices. *Ecol. Econ.* 198, 107440.
- Böcker, T., Möhring, N., Finger, R., 2019. Herbicide free agriculture? A bio-economic modelling application to Swiss wheat production. *Agric. Syst.* 173, 378–392.
- Böcker, T., Britz, W., Möhring, N., Finger, R., 2020. An economic and environmental assessment of a glyphosate ban for the example of maize production. *Eur. Rev. Agric. Econ.* 47 (2), 371–402.
- Bopp, C., Engler, A., Poortvliet, P.M., Jara-Rojas, R., 2019. The role of farmers' intrinsic motivation in the effectiveness of policy incentives to promote sustainable agricultural practices. *J. Environ. Manag.* 244, 320–327.
- Breitenmoser, S., Steinger, T., Hiltbold, L., Grosjean, Y., Nussbaum, V., Bussereau, F., Baux, A., 2020. Effet des plantes associées au colza d'hiver sur les dégâts d'altises. *Rech Agron Suisse* 11, 16–25.
- Bremmer, J., Reinders, M.J., Riemens, M.M., 2021. The Future of Crop Protection in Europe. European Parliament, Directorate-General for Parliamentary Research Services. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2861/086545>.
- Bub, S., Wolfram, J., Petschick, L.L., Stehle, S., Schulz, R., 2022. Trends of total applied pesticide toxicity in German agriculture. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 57 (1), 852–861.
- Buchholz, M., Musshoff, O., 2021. Tax or green nudge? An experimental analysis of pesticide policies in Germany. *Eur. Rev. Agric. Econ.* 48 (4), 940–982.
- Buurma, J.S., Van Der Velden, N.J.A., 2017. New approach to integrated Pest management research with and for horticulture. A vision from and beyond economics. *Crop Prot.* 97, 94–100.
- Byerly, H., Balmford, A., Ferraro, P.J., Wagner, C.H., Palchak, E., Polasky, S., Ricketts, T. H., Schwartz, A.J., Fisher, B., 2018. Nudging pro-environmental behavior: evidence and opportunities. *Front. Ecol. Environ.* 16 (3), 159–168.
- Candel, J., Pe'er, G., Finger, R., 2023. European agriculture needs ambitious pesticide policies. *Nature Food* 4, 272.
- Carisse, O., Rolland, D., 2004. Effect of timing of application of the biological control agent *Microspora ochracea* on the production and ejection pattern of ascospores by *Venturia inaequalis*. *Phytopathology* 94, 1305–1314.
- Chapman, K.S., Sundin, G.W., Beckerman, J.L., 2011. Identification of resistance to multiple fungicides in field populations of *Venturia inaequalis*. *Plant Dis.* 95 (8), 921–926.
- Chèze, B., David, M., Martinet, V., 2020. Understanding farmers' reluctance to reduce pesticide use: a choice experiment. *Ecol. Econ.* 167, 106349.
- Cook, S.M., Doring, T.F., Ferguson, A.W., Martin, J.L., Skellern, M.P., Smart, L.E., Watts, N.P., Welham, S.J., Woodcock, C., Pickett, J.A., 2013. Development of an integrated pest management strategy for control of pollen beetles in winter oilseed rape. HGCA project report no. 504. <https://cereals.ahdb.org.uk/publications/2013/february/05/development-of-an-integrated-pest-management-strategy-for-control-of-pollen-beetles-in-winter-oilseed-rape.aspx>.

- Creissen, H.E., Jones, P.J., Tranter, R.B., Girling, R.D., Jess, S., Burnett, F.J., Kildea, S., 2019. Measuring the unmeasurable? A method to quantify adoption of integrated pest management practices in temperate arable farming systems. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 75 (12), 3144–3152.
- Crowder, D.W., Reganold, J.P., 2015. Financial competitiveness of organic agriculture on a global scale. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 112 (24), 7611–7616.
- Cui, Z., Zhang, H., Chen, X., et al., 2018. Pursuing sustainable productivity with millions of smallholder farmers. *Nature* 555, 363–366.
- Cuyno, L.C., Norton, G.W., Rola, A., 2001. Economic analysis of environmental benefits of integrated pest management: a Philippine case study. *Agric. Econ.* 25 (2–3), 227–233.
- Danne, M., Mußhoff, O., Schulte, M., 2019. Analysing the importance of glyphosate as part of agricultural strategies: a discrete choice experiment. *Land Use Policy* 86, 189–207.
- Deguine, J.P., Aubertot, J.N., Flor, R.J., Lescourret, F., Wychhuys, K.A., Ratnadass, A., 2021. Integrated pest management: good intentions, hard realities. *A review. Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 41 (3), 38.
- Deguine, J.P., Aubertot, J.N., Bellon, S., Côte, F.X., Lauri, P.E.P.E., Lescourret, F., Lamichhane, J.R., 2023. Agroecological crop protection for sustainable agriculture. *Adv. Agron.* 178.
- Dessart, F.J., Barreiro-Hurlé, J., Van Bavel, R., 2019. Behavioural factors affecting the adoption of sustainable farming practices: a policy-oriented review. *Eur. Rev. Agric. Econ.* 46 (3), 417–471.
- Dueri, S., Mack, G., 2024. Modeling the implications of policy reforms on pesticide risk for Switzerland. *Sci. Total Environ.* 928, 172436.
- El Benni, N., Grovermann, C., Finger, R., 2023. Towards more evidence-based agricultural and food policies. *Q Open* 3 (3), 1–24.
- Engelen, B., 2017. A new definition of and role for preferences in positive economics. *J. Econ. Methodol.* 24, 254–273.
- Engler, A., Poortvliet, P.M., Klerkx, L., 2019. Toward understanding conservation behavior in agriculture as a dynamic and mutually responsive process between individuals and the social system. *J. Soil Water Conserv.* 74 (4), 74A–80A.
- EU Commission, 2020. **Farm to Fork Strategy, for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system.** https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-05/f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf.
- European Court of Auditors, 2020. Sustainable Use of Plant Protection Products: Limited Progress in Measuring and Reducing Risks. Special report 05/2020. European Court of Auditors, Luxembourg, Luxembourg.
- Ewert, F., Baatz, R., Finger, R., 2023. Agroecology for a sustainable agriculture and food system – from local solutions to large-scale adoption. *Ann. Rev. Resour. Econ.* 15, 351–381.
- Fan, X., Gómez, M.I., Atallah, S.S., Conrad, J.M., 2020. A Bayesian state-space approach for invasive species management: the case of spotted wing drosophila. *Am. J. Agric. Econ.* 102 (4), 1227–1244.
- Finger, R., 2021. No pesticide free Switzerland. *Nature Plants* 7, 1324–1325.
- Finger, R., 2023. Digital innovations for sustainable and resilient agricultural systems. *Eur. Rev. Agric. Econ.* 50 (4), 1277–1309.
- Finger, R., 2024a. Europe's ambitious pesticide policy and its impact on agriculture and food systems. *Agric. Econ.* 55 (2), 265–269.
- Finger, R., 2024b. On the definition of pesticide-free crop production systems. *Agric. Syst.* 214, 103844.
- Finger, R., Möhring, N., 2022. The adoption of pesticide-free wheat production and farmers' perceptions of its environmental and health effects. *Ecol. Econ.* 198, 107463.
- Finger, R., Möhring, N., 2024. The emergence of pesticide-free crop production systems in Europe. *Nature Plants* 10, 360–366.
- Finger, R., Möhring, N., Dalhaus, T., Böcker, T., 2017. Revisiting pesticide taxation schemes. *Ecol. Econ.* 134, 263–266.
- Finger, R., Zachmann, L., McCallum, C., 2023a. Short supply chains and the adoption of fungus-resistant grapevine varieties. *Appl. Econ. Perspect. Policy* 45 (3), 1753–1775.
- Finger, R., Wüpper, D., McCallum, C., 2023b. The (in)stability of farmer risk preferences. *J. Agric. Econ.* 74, 155–167.
- Finger, R., Schneider, K., Candel, J., Möhring, N., 2024a. Europe needs better pesticide policies to reduce impacts on biodiversity. *Food Policy* 125, 102632.
- Finger, R., Garcia, V., McCallum, C., Rommel, J., 2024b. A note on European farmers' preferences under cumulative prospect theory. *J. Agric. Econ.* 75 (1), 465–472.
- Focks, Andreas, Lageschaar, Luuk, Leendertse, Peter, Helmes, Roel, Bremmer, Johan, 2023. Environmental Indicator Crop Protection (EICP); documentation of calculation rules. Wageningen Wageningen Econ. Res. Rep. 46, 2023–015.
- Foolen-Torgerson, K., Lagerkvist, C.J., Sok, J., Dicke, M., Oude Lansink, A., 2023. Cultivating choices: how social context shapes farmers' considerations in crop and soil health promoter selection. *NJAS Impact Agricult. Life Sci.* 95 (1), 2256694.
- Gaba, S., Bretagnolle, V., 2020. Social–ecological experiments to foster agroecological transition. *People Nature* 2 (2), 317–327.
- Garcia, V., Niklas, M., Wang, Y., Finger, R., 2024. Risk perceptions, preferences and the adoption dynamics of pesticide-free production. *J. Agric. Resour. Econ.* 49 (1), 102–123.
- Gent, D.H., De Wolf, E., Pethybridge, S.J., 2011. Perceptions of risk, risk aversion, and barriers to adoption of decision support systems and integrated pest management: an introduction. *Phytopathology* 101 (6), 640–643.
- Guinet, M., Adeux, G., Cordeau, S., Courson, E., Nandillon, R., Zhang, Y., Munier-Jolain, N., 2023. Fostering temporal crop diversification to reduce pesticide use. *Nat. Commun.* 14, 7416.
- Hill, S.B., MacRae, R.J., 1996. Conceptual framework for the transition from conventional to sustainable agriculture. *J. Sustain. Agric.* 7 (1), 81–87.
- Holb, I., 2009. Fungal disease management in environmentally friendly apple production - a review. In: Lichtfouse, E. (Ed.), *Sustainable Agricultural Reviews Vol. 2. Climate Change, Inter cropping, Pest Control and Beneficial Microorganisms*, pp. 219–292.
- Howley, P., Ocean, N., 2022. Can nudging only get you so far? Testing for nudge combination effects. *Eur. Rev. Agric. Econ.* 49 (5), 1086–1112.
- Huber, R., Xiong, H., Keller, K., Finger, R., 2022. Bridging behavioural factors and standard bio-economic modelling in an agent-based modelling framework. *J. Agric. Econ.* 73 (1), 35–63.
- Huber, R., Späti, K., Finger, R., 2023. A behavioural agent-based modelling approach for the ex-ante assessment of policies supporting precision agriculture. *Ecol. Econ.* 212, 107936.
- Iyer, P., Bozzola, M., Hirsch, S., Meraner, M., Finger, R., 2020. Measuring farmer risk preferences in Europe: a systematic review. *J. Agric. Econ.* 71 (1), 3–26.
- Jacquet, F., Butault, J.P., Guichard, L., 2011. An economic analysis of the possibility of reducing pesticides in French field crops. *Ecol. Econ.* 70 (9), 1638–1648.
- Jacquet, F., Jeuffroy, M.H., Jouan, J., Le Cadre, E., Litrico, I., Malausa, T., Huyghe, C., 2022. Pesticide-free agriculture as a new paradigm for research. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 42 (1), 8.
- Jørgensen, L.N., Kudsk, P., Ørum, J.E., 2019. Links between pesticide use pattern and crop production in Denmark with special reference to winter wheat. *Crop Prot.* 119, 147–157.
- Junyu, Lu, Ranjan, P., Floress, K., Arbuckle, J.G., Church, S.P., Eanes, F.R., Gao, Y., Gramig, B.M., Singh, A.S., Prokopy, L.S., 2022. A meta-analysis of agricultural conservation intentions, behaviors, and practices: insights from 35 years of quantitative literature in the United States. *J. Environ. Manag.* 323, 116240.
- Kathage, J., Castañera, P., Alonso-Prados, J.L., Gómez-Barbero, M., Rodríguez-Cerezo, E., 2018. The impact of restrictions on neonicotinoid and fipronil insecticides on pest management in maize, oilseed rape and sunflower in eight European Union regions. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 74, 88–99.
- Knapp, L., Mazzi, D., Finger, R., 2019. Management strategies against *Drosophila suzukii*: insights into Swiss grape growers choices. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 75 (10), 2820–2829.
- Knapp, L., Wuepper, D., Finger, R., 2021. Preferences, personality, aspirations, and farmer behavior. *Agric. Econ.* 52 (6), 901–913.
- Knowler, D., Bradshaw, B., 2007. Farmers' adoption of conservation agriculture: a review and synthesis of recent research. *Food Policy* 32, 25–48.
- Kreft, C., Huber, R., Schäfer, D., Finger, R., 2023. Quantifying the impact of farmers' social networks on the effectiveness of climate change mitigation policies in agriculture. *J. Agric. Econ.* <https://doi.org/10.1111/1477-9552.12557>. In Press.
- Kudsk, P., Jensen, J.E., 2014. Experiences with implementation and adoption of integrated pest management in Denmark. In: *Integrated Pest Management: Experiences with Implementation, Global Overview*, vol. 4, pp. 467–485.
- Kudsk, P., Jørgensen, L.N., Ørum, J.E., 2018. Pesticide load—a new Danish pesticide risk indicator with multiple applications. *Land Use Policy* 70, 384–393.
- Kuehne, G., Llewellyn, R., Pannell, D.J., Wilkinson, R., Dolling, P., Ouzman, J., Ewing, M., 2017. Predicting farmer uptake of new agricultural practices: a tool for research, extension and policy. *Agric. Syst.* 156, 115–125.
- Kuntosch, A., König, B., 2018. Linking system perspectives with user perspectives to identify adoption barriers to food security innovations for smallholder farmers—evidence from rural Tanzania. *Food Secur.* 10, 881–896.
- Kvakkestad, V., Steiro, Å.L., Vatn, A., 2021. Pesticide policies and farm behavior: the introduction of regulations for integrated pest management. *Agriculture* 11 (9), 828.
- Lacoste, M., Cook, S., McNeen, M., Gale, D., Ingram, J., Bellon-Maurel, V., Hall, A., 2022. On-farm experimentation to transform global agriculture. *Nature Food* 3 (1), 11–18.
- Laloi, G., Vergne, E., Durel, C.E., Le Cam, B., Caffer, V., 2017. Efficiency of pyramiding of three quantitative resistance loci to apple scab. *Plant Pathol.* 66 (3), 412–422.
- Läpple, D., Kelley, H., 2015. Spatial dependence in the adoption of organic drystock farming in Ireland. *Eur. Rev. Agric. Econ.* 42 (2), 315–337.
- Läpple, D., Van Rensburg, T., 2011. Adoption of organic farming: are there differences between early and late adoption? *Ecol. Econ.* 70 (7), 1406–1414.
- Larsen, A.E., Gaines, S.D., Deschênes, O., 2017. Agricultural pesticide use and adverse birth outcomes in the San Joaquin Valley of California. *Nat. Commun.* 8 (1), 302.
- Lefebvre, M., Langrell, S.R., Gomez-y-Paloma, S., 2015. Incentives and policies for integrated pest management in Europe: a review. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 35, 27–45.
- Levidov, L., Bijman, J., 2002. Farm inputs under pressure from the European food industry. *Food Policy* 27, 31–45.
- Liebman, M., Gallandt, E.R., 1997. Many little hammers: Ecological management of crop-weed interactions. In: Jackson, L.E. (Ed.), *Ecology in Agriculture*. Academic, San Diego, CA, pp. 291–343.
- Mack, G., Finger, R., Ammann, J., El Benni, N., 2023. Modelling policies towards pesticide-free agricultural production systems. *Agric. Syst.* 207, 103642.
- Maertens, A., 2017. Who cares what others think (or do)? Social learning and social pressures in cotton farming in India. *Am. J. Agric. Econ.* 99 (4), 988–1007.
- Meemken, E.M., Qaim, M., 2018. Organic agriculture, food security, and the environment. *Ann. Rev. Resour. Econ.* 10, 39–63.
- Mesnager, R., Straw, E.A., Antoniou, M.N., Benbrook, C., Brown, M.J., Chauzat, M.P., Zioga, E., 2021. Improving pesticide-use data for the EU. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* 5 (12), 1560.
- Midingoyi, S.K.G., Kassie, M., Muriithi, B., Diro, G., Ekesi, S., 2019. Do farmers and the environment benefit from adopting integrated pest management practices? Evidence from Kenya. *J. Agric. Econ.* 70 (2), 452–470.
- Milner, A.M., Boyd, I.L., 2017. Toward pesticide vigilance. *Science* 357 (6357), 1232–1234.
- Möhring, N., Finger, R., 2022. Pesticide-free but not organic: adoption of a large-scale wheat production standard in Switzerland. *Food Policy* 106, 102188.
- Möhring, N., Gaba, S., Finger, R., 2019. Quantity based indicators fail to identify extreme pesticide risks. *Sci. Total Environ.* 646, 503–523.

- Möhring, N., Ingold, K., Kudsk, P., Martin-Laurent, F., Niggli, U., Siegrist, M., Studer, B., Walter, A., Finger, R., 2020a. Pathways for advancing pesticide policies. *Nature Food* 1, 535–540.
- Möhring, N., Bozzola, M., Hirsch, S., Finger, R., 2020b. Are pesticides risk decreasing? The relevance of pesticide indicator choice in empirical analysis. *Agric. Econ.* 51 (3), 429–444.
- Möhring, N., Kanter, D., Aziz, T., Castro, I.B., Maggi, F., Schulte-Uebbing, L., Seufert, V., Tang, F.H., Zhang, X., Leadley, P., 2023a. Successful implementation of global targets to reduce nutrient and pesticide pollution requires suitable indicators. *Nat. Ecol. Evol.* 1–4.
- Möhring, N., Huber, R., Finger, R., 2023b. Combining ex-ante and ex-post assessments to support the sustainable transformation of agriculture: the case of Swiss pesticide-free wheat production. *Q Open* 3 (3), qoac022.
- Möhring, et al., 2024. Global Assessment Reveals Multiple Win-Win Situations from Sustainable Crop Protection (Submitted).
- Möhring, N., Kudsk, P., Jørgensen, L.N., Ørum, J.E., Finger, R., 2021. An R package to calculate potential environmental and human health risks from pesticide applications using the ‘Pesticide Load’ indicator applied in Denmark. *Comput. Electron. Agric.* 191, 106498.
- Ortega-Ramos, P.A., Coston, D.J., Seimandi-Corda, G., Mauchline, A.L., Cook, S.M., 2022. Integrated pest management strategies for cabbage stem flea beetle (*Psylliodes chrysocephala*) in oilseed rape. *GCB Bioenergy* 14, 267–286.
- Osteen, C.D., Fernandez-Cornejo, J., 2013. Economic and policy issues of US agricultural pesticide use trends. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 69 (9), 1001–1025.
- Oude Lansink, A., Schut, M., Kamanda, J., Klerkx, L., 2018. A multi-level and multi-actor approach to risk governance: a conceptual framework to support policy development for Ambrosia weed control. *J. Risk Res.* 21, 780–799.
- Owen, M.D., Beckie, H.J., Leeson, J.Y., Norsworthy, J.K., Steckel, L.E., 2015. Integrated pest management and weed management in the United States and Canada. *Pest Manag. Sci.* 71 (3), 357–376.
- Pannell, D.J., 1991. Pests and pesticides, risk and risk aversion. *Agric. Econ.* 5 (4), 361–383.
- Pannell, D., Marshall, G., Barr, N., Curtis, A., Vanclay, F., Wilkinson, R., 2006. Understanding and promoting adoption of conservation technologies by rural landholders. *Aust. J. Exp. Agric.* 46, 1407–1424.
- Parisi, L., Gros, C., Combe, F., Parveaud, C.-E., Gomez, C., Brun, L., 2013. Impact of a cultivar mixture on scab, powdery mildew and rosy aphid in an organic apple orchard. *Crop Prot.* 43, 207–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2012.09.014>.
- Parsa, S., Morse, S., Bonifacio, A., Chancellor, T.C., Condori, B., Crespo-Pérez, V., Dangles, O., 2014. Obstacles to integrated pest management adoption in developing countries. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 111 (10), 3889–3894.
- Passey, T., Xu, X., 2019. Epidemiology and management of apple scab. In: Xu, X., Fountain, M. (Eds.), *Integrated Management of Diseases and Insect Pests of Tree Fruit*, pp. 3–20.
- Patocchi, A., Wehrli, A., Dubuis, P.H., Auwerkerken, A., Leida, C., Cipriani, G., Passey, T., Staples, M., Didelot, F., Philion, V., Peil, A., 2020. Ten years of VINQUEST: first insight for breeding new apple cultivars with durable apple scab resistance. *Plant Dis.* 104 (8), 2074–2081.
- Peerlings, J., Polman, N., 2009. Farm choice between Agri-environmental contracts in the European Union. *J. Environ. Plan. Manag.* 52, 593–612.
- Polman, N., Slangen, L., 2008. Institutional design of Agri-environmental contracts in the European Union: the role of trust and social capital. *NJAS Wageningen J. Life Sci.* 55, 413–430.
- Prokopy, L.S., Floress, K., Klotthor-Weinkauff, D., Baumgart-Getz, A., 2008. Determinants of agricultural best management practice adoption: evidence from the literature. *J. Soil Water Conserv.* 63 (5), 300–311.
- Rebaudo, F., Carpio, C., Crespo-Pérez, V., Herrera, M., de Scurrah, M.M., Canto, R.C., Dangles, O., 2014. Agent-based models and integrated pest management diffusion in small scale farmer communities. In: *Integrated Pest Management: Experiences with Implementation*, Global Overview, vol. 4, pp. 367–383.
- Reidsma, P., Janssen, S., Jansen, J., van Ittersum, M.K., 2018. On the development and use of farm models for policy impact assessment in the European Union—a review. *Agric. Syst.* 159, 111–125.
- Riemens, M., Sønderkov, M., Moonen, A.C., Storkey, J., Kudsk, P., 2022. An integrated weed management framework: a pan-European perspective. *Eur. J. Agron.* 133, 126443 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2021.126443>.
- Roberts, A.L., Crute, I.R., 1994. Apple scab resistance from *Malus floribunda* 821 (Vf) is rendered ineffective by isolates of *Venturia inaequalis* from *Malus floribunda*. *Norwegian J. Agric. Sci.* 17, 403–406.
- Rodenburg, J., Schut, M., Demont, M., Klerkx, L., Gbèhounou, G., Oude Lansink, A., Mourits, M., Rotteveel, T., Kayeke, J., van Ast, A., Akanvou, L., Cissoko, M., Kamanda, J., Bastiaans, L., 2015. Systems approaches to innovation in pest management: reflections and lessons learned from an integrated research program on parasitic weeds in rice. *Int. J. Pest Manag.* 61, 329–339.
- Runge, T., Latacz-Lohmann, U., Schaller, L., Todorova, K., Daughbjerg, C., Termansen, M., Velazquez, F.J.B., 2022. Implementation of eco-schemes in fifteen European Union member states. *EuroChoices* 21 (2), 19–27.
- Sarwosi, A.W., Mußhoff, O., 2020. Are risk attitudes and time preferences crucial factors for crop diversification by smallholder farmers? *J. Int. Dev.* 32, 922–942.
- Schaub, S., Ghazoul, J., Huber, R., Zahng, W., Sander, A., Rees, C., Naerjee, S., Finger, R., 2023. The role of behavioral factors and opportunity costs in farmers’ participation in voluntary Agri-environmental schemes: a systematic review. *J. Agric. Econ.* 74 (3), 617–660.
- Schebesta, H., Candel, J.J., 2020. Game-changing potential of the EU’s farm to fork strategy. *Nature Food* 1 (10), 586–588.
- Schneider, K., Barreiro-Hurle, J., Rodriguez-Cerezo, E., 2023. Pesticide reduction amidst food and feed security concerns in Europe. *Nature Food* 4 (9), 746–750.
- Schulz, R., Bub, S., Petschick, L.L., Stehle, S., Wolfram, J., 2021. Applied pesticide toxicity shifts toward plants and invertebrates, even in GM crops. *Science* 372 (6537), 81–84.
- Schut, M., Rodenburg, J., Klerkx, L., van Ast, A., Bastiaans, L., 2014. Systems approaches to innovation in crop protection. A systematic literature review. *Crop Protect.* 56, 98–108.
- Sexton, S.E., Lei, Z., Zilberman, D., 2007. The economics of pesticides and pest control. *Int. Rev. Environ. Resour. Econ.* 1 (3), 271–326.
- Shiferaw, B.A., Kebede, T.A., You, L., 2008. Technology adoption under seed access constraints and the economic impacts of improved pigeonpea varieties in Tanzania. *Agric. Econ.* 39 (3), 309–323.
- Skellern, M.P., Cook, S.M., 2018. Prospects for improved off-crop habitat management for pollen beetle control in oilseed rape. *Arthropod Plant Interact.* 12, 849–866.
- Skevas, T., Stefanou, S.E., Lansink, A.O., 2013. Do farmers internalise environmental spillovers of pesticides in production? *J. Agric. Econ.* 64 (3), 624–640.
- Sok, J., Borges, J.R., Schmidt, P., Ajzen, I., 2021. Farmer behaviour as reasoned action: a critical review of research with the theory of planned behaviour. *J. Agric. Econ.* 72, 388–412.
- Song, F., Swinton, S.M., 2009. Returns to integrated pest management research and outreach for soybean aphid. *J. Econ. Entomol.* 102 (6), 2116–2125.
- Strassemeyer, J., Daehmlow, D., Dominic, A.R., Lorenz, S., Golla, B., 2017. SYNOPSIS-WEB, an online tool for environmental risk assessment to evaluate pesticide strategies on field level. *Crop Prot.* 97, 28–44.
- Sun, H., Hurley, T.M., Dentzman, K., Ervin, D.E., Everman, W., Frisvold, G.B., Owen, M., 2017. Economic and Behavioral Drivers of Herbicide Resistance Management in the US. *Proceedings of the Agricultural and Applied Economics Association (AAEA) Conferences 2017 Annual Meeting, July 30–August 1, Chicago, Illinois*. <https://doi.org/10.22004/ag.econ.258417>.
- Sutton, D.K., MacHardy, W.E., Lord, W.G., 2000. Effect of leaf shredding or treating apple leaves litter with urea on ascospore dose of *Venturia inaequalis* and disease buildup. *Plant Dis.* 84, 1319–1326.
- Swanton, C.J., Mahoney, K.J., Chandler, K., Gulden, R.H., 2008. Integrated weed management: knowledge-based weed management systems. *Weed Sci.* 56, 168–172.
- Tang, F.H., Lenzen, M., McBratney, A., Maggi, F., 2021. Risk of pesticide pollution at the global scale. *Nat. Geosci.* 14 (4), 206–210.
- Thompson, B., Leduc, G., Manevska-Tasevska, G., Toma, L., Hansson, H., 2024. Farmers’ adoption of ecological practices: a systematic literature map. *J. Agric. Econ.* 75 (1), 84–107.
- Topping, C.J., Aldrich, A., Berny, P., 2020. Overhaul environmental risk assessment for pesticides. *Science* 367 (6476), 360–363.
- Tsiafouli, M.A., Thébault, E., Sgardelis, S.P., De Ruiter, P.C., Van Der Putten, W.H., Birkhofer, K., Hedlund, K., 2015. Intensive agriculture reduces soil biodiversity across Europe. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 21 (2), 973–985.
- Ulber, B., Williams, I.H., Klukowski, Z., Luik, A., Nilsson, C., 2010. Parasitoids of oilseed rape pests in Europe: Key species for conservation biocontrol. In: Williams, I.H. (Ed.), *Biocontrol-Based Integrated Management of Oilseed Rape Pests*. Springer, London, pp. 45–76.
- Uthes, S., Heyer, I., Kaiser, A., Zander, P., Bockstaller, C., Desjeux, Y., Juchniewicz, M., 2019. Costs, quantity and toxicity: comparison of pesticide indicators collected from FADN farms in four EU-countries. *Ecol. Indic.* 104, 695–703.
- Van Lenteren, J.C., 2001. Harvesting safely from biodiversity: Natural enemies as sustainable and environmentally friendly solutions for pest control. In: *Balancing Nature: Assessing the Impact of Importing Non-native Biological Control Agents (an International Perspective)*. Entomological Society of America, p. 15.
- Verret, V., Gardarin, A., Makowski, D., Lorin, M., Cadoux, S., Butier, A., Valantin-Morison, M., 2017. Assessment of the benefits of frost-sensitive companion plants in winter rapeseed. *Eur. J. Agron.* 91, 93–103.
- Vroljik, H., Poppe, K., 2021. Cost of extending the farm accountancy data network to the farm sustainability data network: empirical evidence. *Sustainability* 13 (15), 8181.
- Waddington, H., Sniltveit, B., Hombrods, J., Vojtkova, M., Phillips, D., Davies, P., White, H., 2014. Farmer field schools for improving farming practices and farmer outcomes: a systematic review. *Campbell Syst. Rev.* 10 (1), i–335.
- Walsh, M., Ouzman, J., Newman, P., Powles, S., Llewellyn, R., 2017. High levels of adoption indicate that harvest weed seed control is now an established weed control practice in Australian cropping. *Weed Technol.* 31, 341–347.
- Wang, Y., Finger, R., 2023. Pest prevention, risk and risk management: the case of *Drosophila suzukii*. *J. Agricult. Appl. Econ.* 2 (1), 98–113.
- Wang, S., Höhler, J., Ang, F., Oude Lansink, A., 2023a. Dutch dairy farmers’ adoption of climate mitigation measures – the role of socio-psychological and socio-demographical factors. *J. Clean. Prod.* 427, 139187.
- Wang, Y., Möhring, N., Finger, R., 2023b. When my neighbors matter: spillover effects in the adoption of large-scale pesticide-free wheat production. *Agric. Econ.* 54 (2), 256–273.
- Waterfield, G., Zilberman, D., 2012. Pest management in food systems: an economic perspective. *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.* 37, 223–245.
- Weltin, M., Zasada, I., Hüttel, S., 2021. Relevance of portfolio effects in adopting sustainable farming practices. *J. Clean. Prod.* 313, 127809.
- White, S., Ellis, S., Pickering, F., Leybourne, D., Corkley, I., Kendall, S., Collins, L., Newbert, M., Cotton, L., Phillips, R., 2020. Project report no. 623 integrated pest management of cabbage stem flea beetle in oilseed rape. In: *AHDB Cereals and Oilseeds*, 623.
- Wuepper, D., Finger, R., 2023. Regression discontinuity designs in agricultural and environmental economics. *Eur. Rev. Agric. Econ.* 50 (1), 1–28.

- Wuepper, D., Roleff, N., Finger, R., 2021. Does it matter who advises farmers? Pest management choices with public and private extension. *Food Policy* 101995.
- Wuepper, D., Tang, F.H., Finger, R., 2023a. National leverage points to reduce global pesticide pollution. *Glob. Environ. Chang.* 78, 102631.
- Wuepper, D., Bukchin-Peles, S., Just, D., Zilberman, D., 2023b. Behavioral agricultural economics. *Appl. Econ. Perspect. Policy* 45 (4), 2094–2105.
- Wuepper, D., Henzmann, S., Finger, R., 2023c. Measuring farmer time preferences: a systematic literature review for Europe and North America. *J. Agricult. Appl. Econ. Assoc.* 2 (4), 823–837.
- Xu, X.-M., Gao, L.-Q., Yang, J.-R., 2010. Are insensitivities of *Venturia inaequalis* to myclobutanil and fenbuconazole correlated? *Crop Prot.* 29 (2), 183–189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2009.07.002>.
- Zachmann, L., McCallum, C., Finger, R., 2023. Nudging farmers towards low-pesticide practices: evidence from a randomized experiment in viticulture. *J. Agricult. Appl. Econ. Assoc.* 2 (3), 497–514.